

***Assessing Financial Health and Restructuring Strategies:
An Empirical Study of Loss-Making State-Owned
Enterprises in Pakistan***

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To my younger self

Abstract

State-owned Enterprises (SOEs) play a crucial role in the economic activity of any country of the world. The SOEs in Pakistan is also an important part of its economy and are the reason behind socio-economic development in the country. There is a total of 212 SOEs in Pakistan, of which 85 are commercial SOEs. Despite their critical role in the economy, these commercial SOEs are becoming a burden on the Government of Pakistan due to their huge losses. These SOEs are incurring losses due to their deteriorating financial health. This research project is motivated to find the factors that are affecting the financial health of these SOEs in Pakistan and also find ways of restructuring them. To find the answers to the research objectives, this research employs the purposive sampling method to collect the data from 30 loss-making SOEs in Pakistan, period 2015 to 2019. The data analysis has been done through a linear regression model and its management is done through SPSS Amos 13 software. To get deep insights regarding each loss-making SOE, the desk review has also been employed. This review has helped to get ways of restructuring these companies. On the basis of desk review findings, we provided the recommendations on each loss-making SOEs in Pakistan. The result of the research model showed that accrual-based earnings management and firm size have a significant impact on financial health. This means that the management of SOEs is involved in the manipulation activities and financial statements are not reflecting their true image. The results also tell increasing the business scale will improve the financial health which means the SOEs which have good asset capability, will have better financial health particularly due to optimal opportunities that are supported through a more economic business scale and control on utilization of resources. Moreover, the emergence of market-based solutions is also required to improve the service delivery of these SOEs and there is a need for the evolution of institutional arrangements such as regulatory frameworks, reviewed from time to time to evaluate the SOEs' sustainability for their retention under government control and ownership.

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CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

State-owned Enterprise (SOE) refers to commercial and non-commercial public-sector corporations, Development Finance Institutions (DFIs), authorities, and Public Sector Companies (PSCs) as defined in the Public Sector Corporate Governance Rules. The State Owned Enterprises are separate legal entities established by the Government in accordance of law so that they can increase business activities in the country on the behalf of government and increase economic activities however, some of SOEs has been established to perform regulatory functions as well. In our country, c. State Owned Enterprises in Pakistan have been established with aim to accomplish wide range of functions in the economy of Pakistan for instance; to develop and control many industries which were established with aim to promote national interests, increase exports of agricultural items which has excess production like rice and cotton and to regulate the import items, to facilitate the financing like providing credit to industries, farmers and businesses, to create capital and other needed goods for the for industrial engineering and to enhance technological skills (Muhammad Zeeshan Hanif, 2020).

According to the Muhammad Zeeshan Hanif (2020) SOEs can be established in both types of economies like mixed industrial economies and in developing countries with aim to act as a significant mechanism of social and economic policy and help in increasing employment, generating revenue, achieving some social goals, ensuring economic development and keeping the control of state over economy (Hanif, 2020). Aharoni describes State Owned Enterprises in 1981 as SOEs have another function which is to facilitate the operations to reach two contradictory objectives which includes to protect public interest and ensure economic goals, however, SOEs have to perform their functions independently to meet its foundational goal as working independently will bring effectiveness and efficiency in performance of SOEs.

However, State-Owned Enterprises are the significant players in the economy of Pakistan and have a dominant role in the important sectors of the country such as power, railways, aviation, and energy. Their performance plays a vital role in the

economy and the quality of citizen’s life. These enterprises’ revenue contributes 12% of GDP. There are 212 SOEs, incorporation by Federal Government includes all trusts, subsidiaries, and funds. This number consists of 85 Commercial SOEs mainly are in the power, energy, financial, manufacturing, transportation, and trading sectors. These entities are expected to be at least self-sustainable and provide high-quality services. Out of the 85 commercial enterprises, 10 are also listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX) (See appendix 5.1). 44 Non-Commercial, and 83 subsidiaries of these commercial SOEs. These SOEs are categorized into commercial, non-commercial, authorities, development finance institutions, and public sector companies (Finance Division Government of Pakistan , 2021)

The division of SOEs based on the sectors in Pakistan is given in table-1 and Commercial SOEs’ classification is given in Figure-1.

Table-1

Sectors	No: of Companies
Financial	18
Industrial Estate Development & Management	4
Infrastructure, Transport & ITC	12
Manufacturing, Mining and Engineering	14
Miscellaneous	5
Oil & Gas	8
Power	20
Trading & Marketing	4

Source: State-Owned Enterprises Triage: Reforms & Way Forward

Figure-1: Classification of Commercial SOE

Source: State-Owned Enterprises report 2018-19

Historically, the State Owned Enterprises in Pakistan have been facilitating economic activities but in last five years the SOEs have been Cash bleeding which is increasing the financial burden on treasury department of Government of Pakistan. According to Khan (2008) SOEs are facing huge losses due to corruption, over employment, increasing inflation and interest rates, rising fiscal deficit and poor management structure of those State Owned Enterprises.

According Mr. Faisal Saeed Cheema (Director General, Defense Services Audit, and Department of the Auditor General of Pakistan) the successive Pakistani Governments have been trying to address issues related to the State Owned Enterprises

by giving them subsidies and other packages like bailout. However, literature revealed that poor governance is major cause of losses. All these issues can be addressed by improving the financial health of these SOEs. Due to the poor financial health, these SOEs are often liquidated if there is no support from the government.

This research is motivated to determine the factors affecting the financial health of SOEs and ways for restructuring which will be a great input in the shareholders and management decision making process. The financial health of the SOEs is affected due to the negative profitability gap that is low due to the burden of operational expenses incurred in the company. The practice of accrual based earning management, subsidy wisdom, firm size, investments and their leverage, are being selected as independent variables. Previous researches conducted on the financial health such as Ansari, Haron, Ismail, Hartadi (2009) use the measurement method of Althman (1984) which focuses on these aspects as they best describe the financial health of the company. Moreover, this research project also provide descriptive analysis of each loss making SOEs in order to get more in depth insights and recommendations for each particular SOE.

The result of this forgoing study would be an inspiration in the management decision making process, so that each SOEs minimize its dependency on funding by the government. Improving the financial health in management related to financing, it would provide a balance between the environment, financial and society interest and the company would be able to get government and society support in a more viable way of tariff adjustments.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

“The State-Owned Enterprises in Pakistan has been an increasing burden on the economy over the years and drawing billions from the budget of each fiscal year. In 2019, these SOEs incurred Rs. 143 billion loss which could have been used in the development of many other areas of the country. Many measures have been taken and some are in the process to reduce this burden on the economy but these attempts are not directed towards improving the financial health of each loss-making SOEs in

Pakistan. The deteriorating financial health of the particular SOE will not only have an impact on the specific sector but the overall economy. Addressing this problem will not only help to improve the financial health of every State-owned enterprise but also drive the economy towards the path of socio-economic development. This study aims to get empirical evidence on the factors affecting the financial health of State-owned enterprises in Pakistan to improve their performance. Furthermore, it will also identify the significant ways to restructure through the help of in-depth analysis of each loss-making State-owned enterprise in Pakistan”

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Based on the Problem Statement of the study, the following research question will be addressed in this report of FYP:

1. Is there any impact of profitability on the financial health of SOEs in Pakistan?
2. Is there any impact of accrual-based earning management on the financial health of SOEs in Pakistan?
3. Is there any impact of firm size on the financial health of SOEs in Pakistan?
4. Is there any impact of investment on the financial health of SOEs in Pakistan?
5. Is there any impact of leverage on the financial health of SOEs in Pakistan?
6. Is there any impact of subsidy on the financial health of SOEs in Pakistan?
7. How to restructure the loss-making SOEs in Pakistan?

1.4 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

SOEs are incurring losses of around Rs. 143 billion every year (SOE Report , 2018-19) and the rationale of this FYP is to identify loss-making SOEs and sort out the ways to restructure and improve them.

The following are the objective that this project is intended to achieve:

1. To determine the impact of profitability on the financial health of SOEs in Pakistan.
2. To determine the impact accrual based earning management on the financial health of SOEs in Pakistan.
3. To determine the impact of firm size on the financial health of SOEs in Pakistan

4. To determine the impact of subsidy on the financial health of SOEs in Pakistan.
5. To determine the impact of firm size on the financial health of SOEs in Pakistan.
6. To determine the impact of leverage on the financial health of SOEs in Pakistan.
7. To determine the ways to restructure SOEs.

1.5 RESEARCH SIGNIFICANCE

The State-Owned Enterprises have been playing a very critical role in the economy of Pakistan but the financial performance of SOEs have remained disappointing. In year 2018-19 the collective net losses from Commercial SOEs of Rs. 143 billion (See appendix 5.2). According to the SOEs Triage Report (State-Owned Enterprises Triage: Reforms & Way Forward) published by Finance Division of Government of Pakistan on March, 03, 2021, the SOEs has important market existence or position in major sectors of Pakistan Economy like power generation and distribution, energy, aviation, and railways sectors. The overall revenues of all the SOEs in 2018-19 was Rs. 4 trillion (approx.) while the book value of their assets was Rs. 19 trillion.

The revenues in 2018-19 were roughly 10% of nominal GDP. Additionally, SOEs provided employment to more than 450,000 people which constitutes around 0.8% of the total workforce. Moreover, the sum of the losses of top-10 loss-making SOEs contributes around 90% to the total losses of SOEs portfolio each year. NHA, Pakistan Railways, PIA and power sector DISCOs have been among the major, top 10 loss-makings SOEs (See appendix 5.3)

The recent World Bank Report, “Hidden Debt Solutions to Avert the Next Financial Crisis in South Asia,” stated that loss-making SOEs have increasing liabilities each year with a remarkably high percentage. This sector causes a net loss in each two out of three years, which amounts to SOE loans to 8-12% of GDP in recent years. Moreover, the report also detailed that the SOE debt covered by the Government is even higher and difficult to quantify. This has been predicted that if the corrective measures are not taken, then this fiscal cost may reach a more significant level in the next coming years.

1.6 Research scope

However, there are many research papers available addressing loss making issues of State Owned Enterprises published in Pakistan and other countries, the researches about SOEs published in Pakistan have concluded that the Corporate Governance and corruption are the major reason behind losses therefore, there is research gap to research and analyze SOEs losses by using different variables. This MBA Finance Final Year Project is aimed to identify these loss-making SOE entities, variables which are driving them toward losses and analyze the data available and figure out the ways to improve the financial performance of State Owned Companies and give recommendations to minimize losses in future.

CHAPTER 2 LITERATURE REVIEW

1.7 INTRODUCTION

The State-Owned Enterprises remain a relevant and important topic of research despite their inefficiencies and poor performance as it directly impacts the countries' economic activity. A wide literature is found on SOEs which evaluated them in many perspectives but in Pakistan, these researches are constrained to governance, organization, and management. Much literature is being conducted on the performance evaluation of these enterprises but there are enough worldwide researches that mainly focused on many financial aspects of these state-owned enterprises.

1.8 HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

1.8.1.1 Financial Health

A combination of financial indicators has been used to cover the financial health aspect of any company such as activity, liquidity, profitability, and leverage indicator. These indicators help to create some rankings named as healthy & unhealthy category. The financial performance uses the same indicator profitability, leverage, activity, and liquidity to measure the success of the financial performance of the company. There could be a success in one indicator of financial performance but not in the other indicator, so through this, it is difficult to assess the financial performance of the company as a whole. While financial health provides the comprehensive assessment of all the indicators which can be used to determine the success of the company and can be evaluated from time to time, compared with peer companies too. In this study, financial health is used as a dependent variable, followed by the approach suggested by Haron (2009). This study covered all five financial ratios aspects to get the financial health of the companies in the categories whether it is weak, strong, or medium.

1.8.1.2 Profitability

The companies often have some targets related to the profitability each year. This target is a need for these companies to get the set goals, in this way managers can utilize the resources and take actions to achieve those goals or objectives. This support to achieve profitability targets is also required by the financial health. Achieving this target determines and increases the value of the company and helps the shareholders to get the optimal dividend. Mitchell and Bercovitz (2007) suggested that the profitability can be measured through comparing it from year to year, improving its financial health or debt to capital ratio.

According to research by Nur Sayidah, Aminullah Assagaf & Bayu Taufiq Possumah (2019), the Profitability positively and significantly has impact on the health of financial position of the SOEs and it was measured by SPSS software with Amos regression which reveals that both variables have significance level of 0.123 which means the level of profitability does not affect the financial health of SOEs. Furthermore, the report mentioned the reason behind no significance is that profitability achievement has no direct impact on the financial health of SOEs.

H1: The profitability has significant impact on the financial health of SOEs.

1.8.1.3 Accrual Earning Management

Earning management is basically a management action which leads to the goal of achieving the financial health of the company (Assagaf, 2017). It is being used for some specific purposes such as smoothing of income, setting up financial report to support the IPO, acquisition, fulfil the requirements of covenants by bank, building the image of management and many others. The accrual earning based management approach is being used to improve the financial health of the company. It is a corporate strategy with the aim to maximize the value of the company. In same research by Nur Sayidah, Aminullah Assagaf & Bayu Taufiq Possumah (2019), the researchers use hypothesis that “Accrual-based earnings management positively and significantly has impact on the financial health of the SOEs” but analysis does not support hypothesis. Therefore, the accrual transactions and earning management policies have no significant impact on the financial health of SOEs. The reason behind having no

significance is mentioned in a paper that financial health is not defined by the profitability (Sayidah (2019)).

As mentioned by Aminullah Assagaf & Hapzi Ali (2017), the profitability strategies for instance earning management has less significant impact on the financial health of SOEs. Furthermore, the earning management strategies will hurt the long - term financial health of SOE and the earning management could be either by real earning management or/ and accrual earning management.

H2: The accrual earning management has significant impact on the financial health of SOEs.

1.8.1.4 Firm Size

This is an important variable which affects the financial health of any company and help the companies to be more productive. Moving further, the hypothesis used in research “Firm size is the independent variable, and it positively and significantly impacts on the financial health of SOEs”. Regression and correlation analysis does not support the hypothesis and reveal the negative impact of firm size on the financial health of SOEs. The reason behind it was mentioned that the companies are meant for community services to construct and develop better society in real terms (Nur Sayidah, Aminullah Assagaf & Bayu Taufiq Possumah 2019).

As mentioned by Afolabi, Adegboyega & Olabisi (2019), the firm size has positive impact on financial health of companies, but the relationship is not significant as per measures which indicates that the firm size is not the significant measure of financial health of SOEs.

H3: The firm size has significant impact on the financial health of SOEs.

1.8.1.5 Investment

The term investment here is the investment on the assets (growth in a fixed assets) which leads to the growth of the company. The research use variable to investigate the significance level and relationship between the Investment and Financial Health of SOEs. However, the correlation coefficient between the Investment and financial health is 0.075 which is significant, but significance level is

smaller, and investment has less significant impact on the financial health (Nur Sayidah, Aminullah Assagaf & Bayu Taufiq Possumah (2019)).

H4: The investment has significant impact on the financial health of SOEs.

1.8.1.6 Leverage

This indicates the extent by which the company utilizes its borrowed funds and high risky obligation is also a deciding factor behind the company's development rate and its benefits. More leveraged companies are more likely to default and therefore it has great impact on the financial health of the company. The research use Leverage as a variable to check the impact of leverage on financial health of SOEs and the study found that the Leverage has significant impact on the financial health of SOEs as the correlation between the Leverage and the financial health is 0.157 (Nur Sayidah, Aminullah Assagaf & Bayu Taufiq Possumah (2019)).

According to, Afolabi, Adegboyega & Olabisi (2019), there is no significant relationship between the leverage and financial health of companies and this research use debt to equity ratio to measure the leverage and by interest coverage ratio and by using both variables study found no significant relationship between leverage and financial performance of companies.

H5: The leverage has significant impact on the financial health of SOEs.

1.8.1.7 Subsidy

The subsidy is an important factor which assist in the development of the company. The amount of subsidy can be used for research and development which will generate new innovations and increase the sales of the company. The Government provides the subsidy to the SOEs to drive the industry growth, development of social and business sector, achieving other economic benefits such as education, health service provision and in general, welfare of the society. If the subsidy by the government to the SOEs, it will boost the development and progress, ultimately increase the financial health. The hypothesis "Subsidy given by government significantly and negatively has effect on the financial health of the SOEs" was tested

by Regression and Correlation analysis but the results do not the hypothesis and discloses the negative impact of subsidy on financial health which means that the subsidy actually declines the financial health of SOEs and the granting subsidies meanings financing the operations which ultimately decline financial health (Nur Sayidah, Aminullah Assagaf & Bayu Taufiq Possumah (2019)).

As mentioned by Aminullah Assagaf & Hapzi Ali (2017), the Government subsidy has signofiacnt impact on the financial performance of SOE as moderator with the significance level of 0.015. The financial performance of SOEs and Subsidy have negative relationship and SOEs financial health is to be highly contingent with the government subsidy. That means the more subsidies government assign to SOEs the lover their financial health will be.

H6: The subsidy has significant impact on the financial health of SOE.

1.9 **RESTRUCTURING OF SOES**

There are many other options to improve the performance of SOEs such as semi-structured form. This area is being focused on by Gupta which in 2005 investigated the performance of partially privatized firms. It mainly focused on the impact of controlling factors such as management incentives on performance. The methodology used to measure the impact is private ownership lagged share on firm performance. The output shows that partial privatization has a positive impact on productivity, performance, and investment.

Privatization is not always the feasible option for each state-owned enterprise. Choudhury and Khanna (2009) focused on performance improvement without privatization. It also analyzed the strategic role that leadership plays in SOEs. The sample data was from 42 laboratories of multinationals, Indian and US patents, and domestic firms. The methodology used to find the impact of director change was a regression. The findings of this study showed that with appropriate leadership, SOEs can significantly improve their performance. It just requires appropriate policies and reforms regarding SOEs functionality.

Eljelly. A.M.A, (2009) investigated the relationship between corporate performance and firm ownership in Private and Public owned enterprises. The sample consists of Saudi Arabia SOEs and Private companies, data from 2000-2003. The variables used to measure the operating performance were ROA, Net profit margin, return on equity, and sales per employee. The market performance measures were annual stock returns and standard deviation of returns. Pooled regression analysis was used to find the impact and key differences between firms. The study results show that the listed SOEs outperformed the listed private firms in terms of profitability and efficiency. But these efficiencies are also dependent on the factors such as the size of the firm, government ownership magnitude, and the economic sector in which it is operating.

CHAPTER 3 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on the objectives and hypothesis of this research project, the conceptual framework is mentioned in Figure below

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework

CHAPTER 4 METHODOLOGY

1.10 INTRODUCTION

The Project Research Methodology includes the steps or processes taken to analyze the problem statements in the project study. It starts from finding the literature review, research questions, variable selection, data collection, data analysis, results along with discussion, and conclusion as the last step.

1.11 SAMPLE DATA

The sample data has been selected on the basis of purposive sampling method which comprises of total 30 loss making SOEs in Pakistan. The time frame for data variables for this project study is starting from 2014-15 to 2018-19 as the latest SOEs report we have is SOE report 2018-19 which has been published in 2021. The variables are collected from multiple sources which includes SOEs report of last 5 years, SOE Triage Report and last five years' annual financial statements of enterprises (analyzed individually) and is analyzed in Eviews 10 statistical software.

1.12 VARIABLE & MEASUREMENT

In order to analyze the financial health of SOEs in Pakistan, the following measurement variables are being used.

1.12.1 Financial Health

This variable depicts that whether the firm has enough resource to meet its short term obligations. This variable is measured by its proxy using Altman Z score (2000) for private firms:

$$Z - Score = 0.72 * \frac{Working\ Capital}{Total\ Assets} + 0.84 * \frac{Retained\ Earning}{Total\ Assets} + 3.107 * \frac{EBIT}{Total\ Assets} + 0.42 * \frac{Book\ Value\ of\ Equity}{Total\ Liabilities} + 0.998 * \frac{Sales}{Total\ Assets}$$

1.12.2 Profitability/loss

Profit is the main motive for a company's establishment as it enriches its owners. The government, the main stakeholder in SOEs, expects to generate maximum and

positive profits. Profitability helps the companies to improve its financial condition by improving its operating cash flows and facilitates the company to acquire bonds, banks loans and shares. The research conducted by Assagaf in 2016 has calculated profitability by the difference in net income of the current year & net income of the previous year and dividing this difference by net income of the previous year. The formula is as follows:

$$\text{Profitability} = \frac{\text{Net Income}_t - \text{Net Income}_{t-1}}{\text{Net Income}_{t-1}}$$

1.12.3 Earnings Management (EM)

Earnings management is the financial reports' alteration to hide actual performance of the company to mislead the stakeholders (Healy et al. 1999). This study covers the manipulation of information related to accountings that affects the SOEs' quality in financial accountability. The Dechow model (1995) is used to estimate the earning management for each SOE. This equation is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} ACC(it)/TA(t-1) = \\ \alpha + \beta(1)(\Delta REV(t) - \Delta REC(it))/TA(t-1) + \beta(2)PPE(it)/TA(t-1) + \beta(3)CFO/TA(t-1) + \varepsilon(it) \end{aligned}$$

Where:

ACC = Total accruals

TA = Total assets

REV = Amount of revenue

RECV = Amount of receivable

PPE = Amount of property, plant and equipment

CFO = Cash flow from operating activities

1.12.4 Firm Size

This variable denotes the number or capacity of the company's assets at the end of year in the financial statements. The Assagaf (2016) calculated this variable by taking the logarithm of total assets: The formula is as follows:

$$\text{Firm Size} = \text{Log}(\text{Total Assets})$$

1.12.5 Investment

This variable denotes the growth in the fixed assets of the company that are reported at the year-end in the financial statements. This variable is calculated by taking the difference of fixed assets in the current year and fixed assets in the previous year, dividing the difference by the fixed assets in the previous year. The formula (Assagaf, 2016) is as follows:

$$Investment = \frac{PPE_t - PPE_{t-1}}{PPE_{t-1}}$$

1.12.6 Leverage

This variable shows that the company's ratio of debt in comparison to the capital for financing the operations. The measurement of this variable includes dividing the total debt by equity of the company. The formula (Pratheepkanth, 2011) to calculate leverage is as follows:

$$Leverage = \frac{Total\ Debt}{Equity}$$

1.12.7 Subsidy

This variable represents the funding received by the company from the government to cover the losses incurred. This funding is a consequence of the revenue lower the operating cost of the company and received from the revenue and expenditure of the government. The measurement of this variable is based on standard subsidy dependence index by using the following formula (Assagaf, 2017):

$$Standar\ SDI = \frac{Subsidy}{Revenue}$$

1.13 RESEARCH MODEL

The model used to test hypothesis, is given in the following equation of linear regression:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 Profitability_{it} + \beta_2 Accrual\ Earning\ Management_{it} + \beta_3 Firm\ Size_{it} \\ + \beta_4 Investment_{it} + \beta_5 Leverage_{it} + \beta_6 Standar\ SDI_{it} + e_{it}$$

CHAPTER 5 FINDINGS, DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

From this point, the research project is divided into two parts. The first part addresses the first six objective of this research project and the second part discusses the finding based on desk review of financial statement of each loss-making SOEs in Pakistan. The purpose of this desk review is to address the seventh research objective.

1.14PART A: ADDRESSING THE FACTORS DETERMINE THE FINANCIAL HEALTH

1.14.1 FINDINGS

1.14.1.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of dependent and all independent variables. The financial health, dependent variable varies from maximum 46.975 to a minimum -26.564 with a mean value of -0.872, close to the minimum number than maximum. This means that the distribution in the data of this variable is concentrated to the value closer to minimum with the fluctuations of 6.487 from the mean. The Altman Z score states that the firm score less than 1.23, has probability of financial embarrassment is very high. In this case, the mean value of Z-Score is -0.872 which means most of the SOEs in research data has the probability of financial embarrassment is very high.

The Profitability, independent variable has mean value 0.673 with standard deviation 9.910. This means that this variable has very high fluctuations within the limits of minimum value -22.024 and maximum value 97.134. This means that the profitability is concentrated to the minimum value than the maximum. The earning management, second independent variable has mean value -0.002 with standard deviation 1.004 which indicates the low fluctuations as compared to the other variables standard deviation. This fluctuations ranges within the limits of minimum -8.110 and maximum 1.738 which means that data is concentrated more on the maximum value than minimum. The independent variable, firm size has mean value 17.178 with standard deviation 2.519, ranges within the limits of

maximum 22.213 and minimum 12.096. This means the firm size data is more concentrated on the maximum number as compared to minimum.

Investment data ranges from maximum 98.241 to minimum -1.346 with fluctuations about 14.402 and a mean value of 2.836. Leverage data ranges from maximum 128.702 to minimum -143.068 with fluctuations about 27.743 and a mean value of 2.576. Subsidy data ranges from maximum 20.961 to minimum -945.075 with fluctuations about 96.944 and a mean value of 15.704.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Maximum	Minimum	Mean	Std. Dev.
Financial Health	119	46.975	-26.564	-0.872	6.487
Profitability	119	97.134	-22.024	0.673	9.910
Accrual Earning Management	119	1.738	-8.110	-0.002	1.004
Firm Size	119	22.213	12.096	17.178	2.519
Investment	119	98.241	-1.346	2.836	14.402
Leverage	119	128.702	-143.068	2.567	27.743
Subsidy	119	20.961	-945.075	15.704	96.944

1.14.1.2 Correlation

Table 3 shows the correlation between the dependent and independent variables. The first column 1 shows the correlation of financial health with all other independent variables. The financial health has significant correlation with accrual earning management = -0.230 (Sig level 5%) and firm size = 0.146 (Sig level 1%). This means that the financial health has significant negative relationship with accrual earning management and positive correlation with firm size.

The column 2 represents the correlation between profitability and all other independent variables. This variable, Profitability only has significant correlation with investment = 0.230 (Sig level 1%). This means that increasing the investment by 23%, will increase the profitability and vice versa. The column 3 shows the correlation between accrual earning management with other independent variable. This variable has only significant positive correlation with firm size = 0.251 (Sig level 1%). The column 4 shows the correlation between firm size and other independent variables. The firm size has significant positive correlation with subsidy = 0.163 (Sig level 5%).

The investment has significant positive correlation with leverage = 0.172 (Sig level 5%).

Table 3. Correlation Matrix

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Financial Health (1)	1.000						
Profitability (2)	0.005	1.000					
Accrual Earn MGT (3)	-0.230*	0.110	1.000				
Firm Size (4)	0.146**	0.109	0.251**	1.000			
Investment (5)	-0.017	0.230**	0.058	0.115	1.000		
Leverage (6)	0.101	-0.082	0.001	0.033	0.172*	1.000	
Subsidy (7)	0.073	0.004	0.009	0.163*	0.034	0.019	1.000

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (two-tailed); **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed).

1.14.1.3 Hypothesis Testing

Table 4 shows the results of regression model to test the hypothesis of this research. The column 1 shows the regression model having independent variable, financial health and dependent variable, profitability. The profitability regression coefficient is 0.003 with significance 0.953. The Adjusted R squared is very low of this model (-0.008) with significance of F-stat 0.953. This means that the model has no significance and profitability has no impact on the financial health.

The column 2 shows the regression model having independent variable, financial health and dependent variable, accrual earning management. The accrual earning management regression coefficient is -1.487 with significance 0.011. The Adjusted R squared is about 4.4% with significance of F-stat 0.011 (Significance level at 5%). This means that the accrual earning management has significant impact on the financial health. The financial health of the SOE reduces by -1.487 which means the accrual earning management has negative impact on the financial health.

The column 3 shows the regression model having independent variable, financial health and dependent variable, firm size. The firm size regression coefficient is 0.518 with significance 0.012 (Significance level at 5%). The Adjusted R squared is about 3.5% with significance of F-stat 0.012. This means that the accrual earning management has significant impact on the financial health. The financial health of the

SOE reduces by -1.487 which means the accrual earning management has negative impact on the financial health.

The column 4 shows the regression model having independent variable, financial health and dependent variable, investment. The investment regression coefficient is -0.008 with significance 0.855. The Adjusted R squared is very low of this model (-0.008) with significance of F-stat 0.855. This means that the model has no significance and investment has no impact on the financial health.

The column 5 shows the regression model having independent variable, financial health and dependent variable, leverage. The leverage regression coefficient is 0.023 with significance 0.273. The Adjusted R squared is very low of this model (0.002) with significance of F-stat 0.274. This means that the model has no significance and leverage has no impact on the financial health.

The column 6 shows the regression model having independent variable, financial health and dependent variable, subsidy. The subsidy regression coefficient is 0.005 with significance 0.430. The Adjusted R squared is very low of this model (-0.003) with significance of F-stat 0.429. This means that the model has no significance and subsidy has no impact on the financial health.

The Column 7 includes the regression analysis between independent variable, financial health and dependent variables, profitability, accrual earning management, firm size, investment, leverage and subsidy. The accrual earning management and firm size are significantly impacting the financial health with regression coefficient -1.833 (Significant at 1%) and 0.539 (Significant at 5%) respectively. The adjusted R squared is about 6.2% that means the model independent variables explains only 6.2% variation in dependent variable, financial health. The model is significant at 5% which means that the financial health is significantly impacted by the accrual earning management and firm size of the SOE.

Table 4. Hypothesis Testing

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
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Constant	-0.880	-0.877	-9.934	-0.858	-0.937	-0.801	-10.096
	0.141	0.131	0.005***	0.158	0.116	0.183	0.018
Profitability	0.003						0.022
	0.953						0.714
Accrual Earn MGT		-1.487					-1.833
		0.011**					0.003***
Firm Size			0.518				0.539
			0.012**				0.028**
Investment				-0.008			-0.023
				0.855			0.582
Leverage					0.023		0.025
					0.273		0.252
Subsidy						0.005	0.003
						0.43	0.651
Adj. R sq.	-0.008	0.044	0.035	-0.008	0.002	-0.003	0.062
F-Statistics	0.004	6.603	6.445	0.033	1.21	0.628	2.317
Prob. (F-Stat)	0.953	0.011**	0.012**	0.855	0.274	0.429	0.038**
Durbin Watson	1.245	0.93	2.12	1.23	1.25	1.25	0.937
Observation	120	120	148	120	120	120	119

***Significant at 1%, **Significant at 5%, *Significant at 10%.

1.14.2 **DISCUSSION**

The findings from the statistical calculation are expressed through correlation matrix, F-statistics, t-stat, adjusted R squared, and also the regression coefficient. These statistics showed important insights that can be stated in general and also specific to the country. The correlation matrix shows that the independent variables have a strong significant correlation with the financial health of the SOEs, which is a variable, accrual earning management with a significant correlation coefficient -0.230 and firm size with a significant correlation coefficient of 0.146. These results are in coherence with the study conducted on Indonesian State-owned enterprises which also shows the firm size and earning management as significant variables. Moreover, the relationship testing between independent variables and financial health with model 2 F-statistics = 6.603 and Prob. Level of F-statistics = 0.011 and model 3 with F-statistics = 6.445 and Prob. F statistics = 0.012 have significant interaction with the financial health of the SOEs. Meanwhile, other independent variables do not have a significant impact on the financial health of the SOEs. These findings suggest that management of these SOEs should pay attention to the variable with a priority level of significance and direction need to be considered, the negative and positive effect of these variables on the financial health of these SOEs.

The regression coefficient also signifies the magnitude and influence of the independent variable, the significance level of influence and tendency towards negative and positive effect, named earning management and firm size, significant impact of the financial health. The earnings management negatively and significantly impacts the financial health while firm size positively and significantly impacts the financial health. This means that the SOEs manipulation activities which inflate its earnings and do not tell the true image of SOEs, Detroit its financial health while having larger the size of the SOEs, the larger the business scale which improve the financial health of the company.

1.14.3 CONCLUSION

This research study found many important issues particularly related to the financial health and the variables' influence concludes the study as follows: a) the independent variable profitability is negatively affected and shows no significance or the hypothesis of this study is also not supported. This means that the profitability recorded by the SOEs does not reflect the reality which images the finances of these SOEs' actual health. Therefore, any amount of profitability reported in the financial statement of these SOEs report no financial impact on its health. b) The independent variable, accrual-based earnings management has a negative significant impact on financial health. This means that the management of these SOEs is increasingly involved in the accrual-based earning management which is deteriorating the financial health. c) Subsidy has no significant impact on the financial health which means the subsidy provided by the Government just helps in covering the deficit of operating expenses but not for paying debts and financing the investments. This reflects the purpose of subsidy which is an equitable distribution to make the products and services of these SOEs available to the people in low economic strata. The lower selling price affects the profit which is covered by the Government Subsidy. d) Firm size shows a significant impact on the financial health which means that the size is also determining factor of the management's success in improving the financial health of the SOEs. e) Investment is not significantly impacting financial health. The study found that the use of debt in financing the investment does not improve the financial health because the investment of financial feasibility aspect is not analyzed based on the present value of cash inflow which is greater than the present value of cash outflow. The economic

viability approach is being used in this study which focuses on the externalities or social benefit aspects, greater than the social cost. f) Capital structure or leverage has no significant impact on financial health. This is because in terms of financing the long-term investment of SOEs is hardly an obstacle because the financial institutions have full trust in these SOEs as they are guaranteed by the government with the full approval by ministries. The liquidity of SOEs, debt repayment, or interest payments is also not an issue because the SOEs can easily take a new short-term loan to repay their long-term debt. Therefore, the changes in debt to equity or capital have no significant impact on financial health. These results are consistent with research studies conducted on Indonesian State-owned enterprises that make it relevant based on the empirical facts of the SOE (Sayidah et al. 2019; Assagaf and Ali 2017)

1.14.4 IMPLICATIONS & LIMITATIONS

Based on the research findings, the policy implication by shareholders which restricts the manipulation activities against management as well as some set target for management that challenges them to fought and achieve optimal financial health. Concerning the firm size, the policy implementation must provide support for resource utilization and increased authority so that the SOEs can operate at an optimum level of efficiency and improve their financial health.

The main limitation of this study is that this study has used secondary data from the annual financial statements of SOEs and during the study many data related issues were faced for instance, no financial statements published by SOEs, limited data available, missing financial statements and the loss making SOE are not listed on PSX therefore, there is no firm value available for the SOEs. Lastly, the time for conducting study was also limited.

1.15 PART B: FINDINGS BASED ON DESK REVIEW OF EACH LOSS MAKING SOES IN PAKISTAN

This part is based on the financial statement analysis of each loss making State owned enterprise in Pakistan. The findings are derived on the basis of horizontal, vertical and ratio analysis. The loss making SOEs covered in these findings are as follows:

No.	SOE's Name	MINISTRIES
1.	Pakistan International Airlines	MINISTRY OF TRANSPORT & INFRASTRUCTURE
2.	Pakistan Railways	
3.	National Highway Authority	
4.	Pakistan Post office	
5.	Quetta Electric Supply Company	MINISTRY OF ELECTRIC DISTRIBUTION
6.	Multan Electric Supply Company	
7.	Lahore Electric Supply Company	
8.	Faisalabad Electric Supply Company	
9.	Hyderabad Electric Supply Company	
10.	Peshawar Electric Supply Company	
11.	Sukkur Electric Supply Company	
12.	Islamabad Electric Supply Company	MINISTRY OF MANUFACTURING, MINING & ENGINEERING
13.	Pakistan Steel Mills	
14.	Heavy Mechanical Complex Limited	
15.	State Engineering Corporation limited	MINISTRY OF MEDIA & ENTERTAINMENT
16.	Telephone Industries of Pakistan	
17.	Pakistan Broadcasting Corporation	MINISTRY OF OIL & GAS
18.	Pakistan Television Corporation	
19.	Sui Southern Gas Company Limited	MINISTRY OF TRADING & MARKETING
20.	Utility Stores Corporation	
21.	SME Bank	MINISTRY OF FINANCE DIVISION
22.	First Women Bank Limited	
23.	Pak Libya Investment & Holding Company	
24.	Printing Corporation of Pakistan	MINISTRY OF CABINET DIVISION
25.	Pakistan Tourism Development Corporation	
26.	GENCO-III: Northern Power Generation Company	
27.	GENCO-I: Jamshoro Power Company Limited	POWER GENERATION COMPANIES
28.	GENCO-IV: Lakhra Power Generation Company	
29.	GENCO-II: Central Power Generation Company	
30.	Pakistan Textile City	INDUSTRIAL ESTATE DEVELOPMENT

1.15.1 MINISTRY OF TRANSPORT & INFRASTRUCTURE COMPANIES

1.15.1.1 PAKISTAN INTERNATIONAL AIRLINE (PIA)

- PIA's revenue is increasing but not enough to cover the expenses.
- In 2019, the gross profit is almost 7.82 million which includes the aircraft fuel and some other service cost. These costs put away almost 95% of the revenue and majority of this part went in the fuel (See Table 4.1.1.1)

Table 4.1.1.1: VERTICAL ANALYSIS OF INCOME STATEMENT

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Revenue-Net	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Cost of Services						
Aircraft fuel	42%	27%	27%	34%	42%	34%
Others	55%	70%	84%	85%	77%	61%
-Salaries, wages & allowances						
Gross Profit / (loss)	-3%	-3%	10%	19%	19%	-5%
Distribution Cost	4%	5%	6%	5%	5%	4.2%
Administrative Expenses	10%	8%	9%	7%	7%	4.7%
Other Provisions and Adjustments	3%	4%	7%	7%	2%	3%
Exchange Gain / (loss) - Net	-3%	2%	0%	2%	14%	0%
Other Income	0%	-1%	-1%	-1%	-2%	-1%
Loss From Operations						
Finance Costs	13%	13%	13%	17%	14%	8%
Share of Profit / (loss) - Net	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Loss Before Taxation						
Taxation	2%	2%	0%	0%	0%	0%

- The second major expense is Salaries, wages & allowances of services provided. This has been greatly reduced in the last 5 years. Moreover, the remaining 5% revenue covers administration, distribution, finance, and exchange loss costs.
- The highest share in this cost is of administration expense. In 2019, the company paid almost PKR 3.9 million in salaries, wages and allowances of administration which means almost 50% of gross profit is consumed by this account. The analysis also shows that the major expense is salaries, wages and allowance in the distribution, service and administration cost.
- The EBIT is consecutively in losses from the past five years. The finance cost is almost 8% of the revenue which the company is unable to cover in the last five years. The company is paying 65% of finance cost in markup on long term financing which is continuously increasing from 22% of finance cost to 65% in the last 5 years.

Table 4.1.1.2: COMPARISON WITH OTHER AIRLINES

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019

PIA

Average Number of Employees	17,383	16,271	13,947	13,268	12,196	11,740
No of Aircrafts	34	38	38	36	32	32
employee to aircraft ratio	511	428	367	369	381	367

EMIRATES

Average number of employees	56,725	61,205	64,768	62,356	60,282	60,033
No of Aircrafts	142	144	153	156	157	158
Employee to aircraft ratio	399	425	423	400	384	380

SOUTHWEST AIRLINES

Employees	49,583	53,536	56,110	58,803	60,767
No. of Aircrafts	704	723	706	750	747
Employees to aircraft ratio	70	74	79	78	81

- The company has the highest number of employees per aircraft in comparison with some other airlines (See Table 4.1.1.2)
- PIA has the highest debt to equity ratio in 2015 to 2019. This means that the company is using more debt money to run its operations (Figure 4.1.1.1)

- The company has the current ratio less than 1 in 2015 to 2019 and industry average's current ratio is greater than 1. This means that the company is not financially stable and has liquidity problems (Figure 4.1.1.2).

1.15.1.2 PAKISTAN RAILWAYS (PR)

- PR has increasing revenue with increasing expenses both has same growth rate therefore the losses are constant.
- The PR is in gross profit but due to high expenses company is suffering from high net losses.
- In the year 2018-19 PR got 7.94% Excess in gross earnings than Estimated/ budgeted and the major excess earning are from Passenger Earnings with 21.62% which reveals that people are willing to travel via Train (demand side is pretty good) (See Table 4.1.2.1).
- The expenditures are too high which shift gross earnings into losses and major proportion of losses are coming General Admin Expenses and Repair and Maintenance.
- Last 5years PR has consistent in Net loss margin and in year 2018-19 the loss is more than 60% of sales (See Table 4.1.2.2).
- Increasing Finance cost to sales ratio, operating expenses to sales are about 100% and decreasing current ratio.

Table 4.1.2.1: VARIANCE ANALYSIS

Income Statement			
Description	Revenue 2018-19		Variation
	Actual		Excess/ (Shortfall) %

Passenger earnings	29,189,457,721	5,189,457,721	21.62
Freight earnings	18,853,163,057	-996,836,943	-5.02
Other coaching earnings	1,995,348,494	245,348,494	14.02
Sundry earnings	4,469,961,765	-430,038,235	-8.78
Gross Earnings	54,507,931,037	4,007,931,037	7.94

Summary of Budgeted and Actual Expenditure

Description	Actual Expenditure	Excess/ (Saving)	%
General Administration	10,142,036,000	-311,131,000	-2.98
Repair and Maintenance	17,779,699,000	-2,097,895,000	-10.55
Operating Expenses	26,255,239,000	160,810,000	0.62
Other Revenue Expenditure	32,445,412,000	58,601,000	0.18
Improvement and Welfare Expenditure	190,897,000	2,897,000	1.54
Misc Advance	-	54,409,000	
Total	86,867,692,000	2,132,309,000	2.4

Balance Sheet

Particulars	2018-19	2017-18	Variation	Variance%
1. Capital & Net Worth				
(a) Investment by Government		235,645.38	22,373.37	9.49
(b) Cumulative Surplus/ (Deficit)		-36,924.39	-	-
Total Capital & Net Worth		198,720.98	22,373.37	11.26
2. Revenue Reserves				
(a) Depreciation Reserve Fund		37,062.41	636.28	1.72
(b) Improvement Fund		529.39	-	-
(c) Railway Reserve Fund		21,668.76	4,230.72	19.52
Total Revenue Reserves		59,260.56	4,867.00	8.21
3. Long Term Liabilities				
(a) Provident Fund		6,594.50	292.46	4.43

Table 4.1.2.2: RATIO ANALYSIS

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Net Profit/loss margin	-85.35%	73.79%	-101.59%	73.88%	60.12%
Finance cost to sales		1.15%	1.01%	1.38%	1.46%
Operating expense to Sales	131.92%	114.66%	125.28%	71.87%	98.79%

Current ratio 7.24 8.35 4.49 4.16 4.08

1.15.1.3 NATIONAL HIGHWAY AUTHORITY (NHA)

- NHA is one of the top cash bleeding SOE for the Government of Pakistan and it has consistent losses due no growth in revenue as they don't have source of revenue expect toll tax and high expenses due to following reasons:
- In last 5 years there no growth in the revenues of the NHA as they don't have any source to generate enough revenues other than toll taxes. And toll tax is not sufficient to cover all of expenses.
- NHA has gross profit but due to high expenses the SOE is in losses.
- High Operating expenses, in year 2018-19 the operating expense is 501% of revenue.
- High other expenses (the details are missing about these expenses) which increase the overall expenses even more than the operating expenses.
- High finance cost due to high liabilities and in year 2018-19 the finance cost expense is 212% of revenue (See Table 4.1.3.1).

Table 4.1.3.1: Ratio Analysis

	2016	2017	2018	2019
	-			
Net Profit margin	630.19%	-455.65%	-493.16%	-585.67%
Finance cost to sales	208.96%	172.73%	205.94%	212.65%
Operating expense to Sales	71.93%	49.02%	42.83%	501.34%
Current ratio	0.03	0.13	0.02	0.01

- High Loans to construct the roads. The high finance cost and it increases losses.
- Depreciation, roads depreciations for using roads... 5-10% dep. Dep is in general expenses.

1.15.1.4 Pakistan Post Office (PPO)

- The PPO is in losses through the years, in year 2019 the PPO has net loss of 9,135 million and compared with the year 2018 the net losses have been increased by 13%.
- The company is occurring gross losses as well in only year 2019, because their revenue generation is too low compared with COGS. The PPO had COGS in year 2019 because the company has started new services (e-Commerce) which incur cost of goods sold.
- However, the revenue generation is too low compared with competitors (TCS, Leopard), due to the company provides delivery services to around 20 million households and businesses as community service without any cost considerations.
- The PPO has round 13,000 post offices and most of them are in losses due to inefficacy in operations and cash low collection.
- The company has high Operating expenses which is 24% of total Revenue.
- The finance cost is about 1.79% of company's revenue.

1.15.2 MINISTRY OF ELECTRIC DISTRIBUTION COMPANIES

1.15.2.1 QUETTA ELECTRIC SUPPLY COMPANY (QESCO)

- *LOSSES:*
 - 1) Increasing trend in the Distribution losses.
 - 2) Increasing trend transmission and distribution losses.
 - 3) Decreasing number of units sold (in specific years).
 - 4) Excess Transmission and Distribution losses over NEPRA Target.
 - 5) Difference in billing and subsidy modules.
 - 6) Increasing Provision against balances doubtful of recovery.
- Low Sales, net sales is 40,878 thousand in year 2019 when the cost of sales is 75,335 thousands from which the 74,925 thousand is purchase cost of electricity.
- The cost of sales, power purchase price 74,925 thousand among that PPP variable charges are 72,556 thousand and PPP fixed charges are 2,369 thousand. The total units (purchased and generated) 6,264 (thousand KWH) and units sold 4,778

(thousand KWH) at Rs. 12.14 per KWH with the transmission and distribution losses of 23.71% (See Table 4.1.4.1).

- Total Operating cost is 10,812 thousand, among total cost the two accounts are major contributors. The salaries, wages and other benefits 6,145 thousand and the late payments surcharge 3,229 thousand.

Table 4.1.4.1: Ratio Analysis

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
G.P. Ratio	30.89	21.87	5.17	10.45	-2.97
Net Profit Ratio	-51.91	-26.98	-38.95	57.56	-125.43
Current Ratio	0.731:1	0.72:1	0.64:1	0.43:1	0.29:1
Debtors Turnover (Times)	0.44	0.38	0.31	0.29	0.29
Collection Period (Days)	834.17	964.68	1,164.12	1,277	1,245
Payable Turnover (Times)	0.33	0.36	0.36	0.25	0.24
Payment Period (Days)	1,113.70	1,011.22	1,027.51	1,456	1,552

Key Operational Indicators

KPIs IN %AGE

Over Losses	24.2	23.5	22.4	23.7	23.7
Distribution Losses	22.3	21.5	20.9	22.1	25.2
Transmission Loss	1.9	2	1.8	1.6	1.9
Collection Govt.	164.9	70.2	42.1	42.6	48.8
Collection Private	83.9	84.6	85.4	82.6	86.9
Overall Collection	71.6	43.5	25	24.4	22.4

1.15.2.2 MULTAN ELECTRIC SUPPLY COMPANY (MESCO)

- MESCO, the company is in losses since last 5 years, Sales has been fluctuating for instance: sales had shown decreasing from 2014 to 2017 and then revenue start growing slowly from 2017 to 2019 (See Table 4.1.5.1).
- The sales is too low compared with the growth in cost of goods sold therefore, MEPCO suffering from gross losses since last three years.
- The net losses are consistent through the years, currently company is facing 30 million losses.

- The reason behind the huge net losses are high operating cost and operating is high due to high salaries, wages and other benefit expenses, staff retirement benefits expense and allowance for expected credit losses expenses.

Table 4.1.5.1: T& D losses and age of collection

TRANSMISSION & DISTRIBUTION LINE LOSSES								
	2015-2016				2016-2017			
	UNITS RECVD	UNITS BILLED	UNITS LOST	%AGE LOSS	UNITS RECVD	UNITS BILLED	UNITS LOST	%AGE LOSS
Actual	14770	12341	2430	180	15952	13253	2698	183
Prog:	96213	80282	15931	192	102829	85526	17302	194
	2017-2018				2018-2019			
	UNITS RECVD	UNITS BILLED	UNITS LOST	%AGE LOSS	UNITS RECVD	UNITS BILLED	UNITS LOST	%AGE LOSS
Actual	19006	15853	3153	180	19367	16310	3057	168
Prog:	122321	102245	20075	187	130269	109890	20379	178
%AGE COLLECTION								
			PVT	GOVT.	TOTAL			
2015-16			99.19	116.51	99.99			
2016-17			96.04	98.93	96.21			
2017-18					97.27			
2018-19			99.89	98.4	99.8			

1.15.2.3 **LAHORE ELECTRIC SUPPLY COMPANY (LESCO)**

- LESCO, has shown good performance by the increasing the revenue and decrease in net loss. However, the company is in losses since last 5 years.
- The sales grew by 32% in FY-2018-19 (See Table 4.1.6.1).
- In year 2018-19 LESCO shown gross profit after 2 years of gross loss.
- The net loss has been decreased in years 2018-19 (-31,621,000) compared with year 2017-18(-56,635,000).
- The operating expenses are the main reason behind the huge historical losses of LESCO.
- The LESCO has increasing trend of finance cost.

Table 4.1.6.1: Ratio Analysis

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Sales Growth		-18%	9%	26%	32%
Net Profit/ (Loss) Growth		26%	234%	52%	-44%
Gross Margin	8%	2%	-4%	-10%	2%

Net profit(loss) Margin	-5%	-7%	-22%	-26%	-11%
Current Ratio	3.16		1.32	0.91	0.81
Debt to equity ratio	9.41	43.34	-3.33	-2.37	-2.7

1.15.2.4 **FAISALABAD ELECTRIC SUPPLY COMPANY (FESCO)**

- This company is in net losses since last 4 years but their gross margins have been fluctuating in last five years.
- The cost of goods sold surpasses the revenue stream even after the subsidy (tariff differential subsidy).
- The net losses are due to high operating cost which has two main costs which increases the overall operating cost first is distribution cost and second is admiration cost.
- On a balance sheet side the assets has no or minor growth in last 5 years with decreasing trend in current ratio (See Table 4.1.7.1).
- In last 2 years they have negative equity which means their assets are totally financed with liabilities. But they have positive cash flows from operating activities.

Table 4.1.7.1: Ratio Analysis

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Gross Profit margin	13.71%	-1.59%	0.15%	-13.56%	6.99%
Net Profit margin	4.27%	-13.46%	14.47%	-29.13%	-4.25%
Current Ratio	4.62	2.67	2.52	1	0.96
Debt to Equity Ratio	1.06	2.3	5.44	-6.89	-5.07

1.15.2.5 **HYDERABAD ELECTRIC SUPPLY COMPANY (HESCO)**

- From the last 3 years, the electricity sales is increasing and the increment is due to the commercial sale increase but not enough to cover the electricity cost. The large proportion of sales is in residential but it has been decreasing from last 5 years (See Table 4.8.1)

Table 4.1.8.1. : Analysis of Sales each Segment (Based on 2015-2019)

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
ELECTRICITY SALES					
Residential	27%	39%	16%	5%	-3%
Commercial	5%	-23%	16%	18%	26%
Industrial	-3%	-24%	-7%	10%	20%
Agricultural	4%	-5%	-16%	-10%	-46%
Others	13%	-36%	6%	127%	143%
Tariff Subsidy	-45%				

- In 2019, the cost of electricity is about 159% of electricity sales. The highest proportion is of variable charges which has been decreased in 2019.
- The fixed charges also keep increasing and in 2019 it has increased about 31% (See Table 4.1)

Table 4.1.8.2. : Analysis of Electricity Cost Breakup (Based on 2014-2018)

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Electricity Sales	-12%	-24%	6%	11%	13%
PPP-Variable charges	-12%	-37%	24%	30%	-2%
PPP-Fixed Charges	19%	11%	28%	14%	31%
Use of system charges	17%	13%	26%	9%	11%

- Transmission and distribution losses are between 25% - 30% from the last 5 years which fluctuates the sales between 44 million to 35 million. The following is the graphical representation of loss in T&D, bill recovery and allowed T&D loss:

This shows the reason of the company loss is the inefficiency transmission and distribution and bill recovery.

- Salaries and wages are about 20% of electricity sales while retirements are keep increasing and has major proportion of sales (See Table 4.1.8.3)

Table 4.1.8.3 : Major Cost as Percentage of Sales

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
T&D Losses						
(%)	27	27	26	31	30	30
Salaries,	11%	15%	20%	20%	20%	20%
Pension	27%	44%	55%	57%	85%	73%
Free electricity	2%	4%	4%	3%	3%	
Free medical	3%	3%	5%	5%	9%	

1.15.2.6 PESHAWAR ELECTRIC SUPPLY COMPANY

- Unable to recover receivables from Govt. of Azad Jammu and Kashmir (16.521 million)
- PESCO sale at the rate of 12.20 per unit but GoAJK settle at 2.59 per unit
- Subsidy is not provided by the Government to cover transmission and distribution losses. Subsidy and electricity sales both together able to cover cost of electricity (See Table 4.1.9.1)

Table 4.1.9.1 : Vertical Analysis of Income Statement

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Electricity sales to consumers	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Subsidy	35%	38%	40%	40%	76%
Rental and service income	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Amortization	1%	1%	2%	2%	2%
Cost of electricity - restated	-127%	-122%	-138%	-164%	-159%
Other operating expenses	-24%	-35%	-27%	-24%	-24%
Depreciation	-2%	-3%	-3%	-3%	-2%
	-17%	-20%	-26%	-50%	-7%
Other income	4%	5%	5%	6%	5%
Financial income \ expense	-5%	-4%	-3%	-4%	-6%

- In comparison with HESCO, PESCO is more in losses but the transmission and distribution losses are more in PESCO. Percentage of bill recovery is more in PESCO than HESCO.
- The transmission and distribution losses are in between 35% to 39% in the last 5 years. The bill recovery is about 88%. The highest unit purchased is by domestic sector and it has the lowest recovery (See Table 4.1.9.2)

Table 4.1.9.2: PESCO Major Loss Accounts

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Allowed T&D loss	33.77%	32.60%	38.15%	36.56%	38.69%
Billed Amount Recovery			88.60	88.62	87.65
Unit purchased (GWh)		11751	12510.96	14220.3	14301.8
Units Sold (GWh)		7782.91	8432.03	8795.53	9073.56
LOSSES		968.09	4078.93	5424.77	5228.24

1.15.2.7 SUKKUR ELECTRIC SUPPLY COMPANY

- In 2017, the recovery amount is more than 100% which has been reduced drastically in the next 3 years
- Only 35% of billed has been realized from the domestic sector and 60% from the agriculture sector
- The transmission and distribution losses are more than 35% (See Table 4.1.10.1)

- Electricity sales and subsidy from the government both combined were unable to cover the cost of the electricity
- SEPCO has the highest number of domestic consumers. If it improves the recovery from this sector, then the company can achieve high sales.

1.15.2.8 ISLAMABAD ELECTRIC SUPPLY COMPANY

- IESCO sales of electricity and purchase of electricity is on break even
- Gross Profit is positive and a substantial amount due to the subsidy provided by the Government in the last 5 years

Table 4.1.10.1: SEPCO Major Loss Accounts

	2016	2017	2018	2019
T&D loss		37.90%	36.97%	36.27%
Billed Amount Recovery		109.98	63.28	56.54
Unit purchased (GWh)	4168	4457	4,679	4386
Units Sold (GWh)	2414.59	2787.73	2,963	2780.61
LOSSES	1773.82	1694.92	1715.92	1631.02

- From the last 4 years, the company is in losses
- The reason of loss is high cost of electricity which has been increasing and more than 100% of the electricity sales (Table 4.1.11.1)

Table 4.1.11.1 : Vertical Analysis of Income Statement

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Sale of electricity-Net	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Subsidy	13%	32%	10%	9%	12%	13%
	113%	132%	110%	109%	112%	113%
Cost of electricity	-94%	-99%	-106%	-106%	-120%	-103%
Gross Profit	19%	33%	3%	3%	-8%	10%

Amortization	1%	1%	2%	2%	1%	1%
Operating Expenses						
Administrative expenses	-5%	-1%	-8%	-6%	-7%	-6%
Distribution costs	-9%	-8%	-11%	-11%	-13%	-10%
Customer service costs	-1%	-1%	-1%	-1%	-1%	-1%
	-15%	-10%	-20%	-18%	-20%	-16%
Operating Profit	5%	24%	-15%	-14%	-27%	-5%
Other Income	1%	2%	2%	1%	2%	2%
	7%	25%	-13%	-12%	-25%	-3%
Finance costs	-1%	-1%	-2%	-2%	-2%	-1%
	5%	24%	-15%	-14%	-27%	-5%
Taxation	-2%		3%	-1%	-1%	-1%
Current	0%	0%	-1%	-1%	0%	0%
Deferred	0%	0%	4%		0%	0%
Profit after taxation	3%	24%	-11%	-15%	-28%	-6%

- The company is very efficient in transmission and distribution as losses are in between 9% to 8%
- In 2018, the recovery of billed amount dropped from 91 to 87 which has increased the loss amount from 11 million to 27 million. This means that recovery of bill amount has great impact on the losses
- The IESCO is very efficient in bill recovery amount almost 99% (See Table 4.1.11.2)

Table 4.1.11.2: IESCO Major Loss Accounts

	2016	2017	2018	2019
T&D loss		9.03%	8.86%	8.69%
Billed Amount Recovery		91.87	87.61	90.27
Unit purchased (GWh)	9652	10582	11,672	11837
Units Sold (GWh)	8774	9627.55	10,606	10789.05
LOSSES	878	955.09	1067.03	1048.74

1.15.3 MINISTRY OF MANUFACTURING, MINING & ENGINEERING

1.15.3.1 PAKISTAN STEEL MILLS

- Cost of sales is very high and revenue is not enough to cover this expense
- In cost of sales, the major expenses which make this cost very high are as follows (See Table 4.1.12.1):
 1. Salaries, wages, benefits and staff welfare cost is between 22% to 58% of sales cost in the last 5 years
 2. Manufacturing cost is also major expense in this account
 3. Other major expenses are service department cost and fuel, power and gas costs.
- High price of raw material and low capacity utilization

Table 4.1.12.1: Break Up Of Cost of Sales

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Salaries, wages	22%	35%	43%	45%	58%	39%
Chemical etc consumed	2%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Service department costs	27%	29%	39%	38%	45%	37%
Fuel, power and gas	22%	6%	6%	7%	11%	14%
Repairs and maintenance	8%	10%	0%	0%	2%	0%
Stores, Spare parts	2%	1%	1%	1%	0%	0%
Depreciation	2%	3%	5%	4%	6%	4%
Other manufacturing expenses	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%

- PP&E has the highest percentage in the asset portion and the land contributes most in it (Table 4.1.12.2).
- Deferred liabilities are increasing and the payable to SSGCL is very high (22 million in 2020) (Table 4.1.12.2)
- Claims lodged by employees, contractors, suppliers, customers, and others worth 20 million in 2020. (Table 4.1.12.2)

Table 4.1.12.2: Vertical Analysis of Balance Sheet Major Costs

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
ASSETS					
Property, plant & equipment	85%	87%	80%	74%	88%
Investment property	5%	5%	13%	19%	8%
	91%	92%	93%	93%	97%
Stores, spare parts & loose tools	1%	1%	1%	1%	0%
Stock-in-trade	5%	4%	4%	3%	2%
Taxes refundable	2%	2%	2%	2%	1%
Cash & bank balances	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Long-term financing	0%	23%	22%	8%	
Deferred liabilities	13%	14%	13%	5%	
Trade & other payables	30%	32%	30%	13%	
Interest/mark-up accrued	11%	18%	23%	13%	
Short-term borrowings	1%	1%	3%	1%	
Deposits & advances	2%	2%	2%	1%	
Current portion of long-term financing	44%	26%	26%	13%	
Payable to the government of Pakistan	1%	1%	1%	0%	
Provisions	0%	0%	0%	0%	

1.15.3.2 HMC- Heavy Mechanical Complex (Private) Limited

- Heavy Mechanical Complex (Private) Limited is a leading engineering goods manufacturing enterprise in Pakistan.
- The Heavy Mechanical Complex (Private) Limited is in losses since last 7 (2013-19) years however, the loss has been fluctuating throughout the years.
- The HMC is in gross Profit in last 2 years (2018 & 19) due to low cost of goods sold and higher Sales (See Table 4.1.17.1).

- The Net losses of HMC were constant in last 7 years (2013-19) but the ratio of Net Loss Margin has been decreased in last 2 years (2018 & 19).
- The key reason behind the net losses are the high Operating Expenses and the ratio of operating expenses to Sales has increasing trend.
- Finance cost was also high.
- High other expenses, in year 2019 the other expenses was almost 29.64% of sales.
- On balance sheet side, the equity position is in negative due to High Liabilities against Assets.
- The current ratio had been increasing.

Table 4.1.17.1: Ratio Analysis

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Gross Profit (loss) margin	9.04%	10.39%	-81.02%	-81.62%		0.50%	11.32%
Net profit (Loss) margin	-0.91%	0.23%	107.47%	-153.58%		-9.81%	-0.37%
Operating expenses to Sales	8.58%	8.24%	24.68%	71.95%		11.28%	15.83%
Current Ratio	1.05	1.03	1.75	2.23		1.85	1.94

1.15.3.3 State Engineering Corporation (Private) Limited

- SEC is known as the mother of heavy engineering sector of the country. Aim is to develop sound industrial base through indigenous manufacturing of high technology engineering goods and capital machinery items, conforming to international quality standards at competitive rates.
- In year 2019, the SEC has incurred losses of 10 million and in years 2018 it was only 3 million, the reason behind huge increment in losses are decrease in sales, having cost of goods sold (there was no COGS in year 2018), high Operating cost and taxes.

1.15.3.4 Telephone Industries of Pakistan

- The Telephone Industries of Pakistan is a huge complex with aim to meet the requirements of Telecommunication Switching Equipment of the country.

- The company has been occurring losses since 2015 and the losses for company are gross losses and net losses but the gross losses are huge as there least revenue generation compared with the cost of goods sold.
- In year 2019 sales increased by 100% (2 million-2018 to 4 million -2019) , Gross Profit Decreased by 102.4%, Net Profit decreased by 104%, Total assets are decreased by 3.15% and that's why liabilities are also decreased by 13.3% whereas the equity position is already in negative (See table 4.1.4.4.1).
- TIP is in gross profit in 2019 the company recorded gross profit due to low cost of goods sold and in only 2019 gross profit/loss margin ratio is 50% (See Table 4.1.4.4.2).
- The TIP is in Net losses in 2019 net profit/loss margin ratio is -2,500%/
- The key reason behind the net losses are the high Operating expenses and the ratio of Operating Expenses to Sales has increasing trend and in 13,650% in 2019.
- Finance cost was also high and the ratio of Finance cost to Sales also has increasing trend and the ratio is 2,150% in 2019.
- On balance sheet side, the equity position was negative due to High Liabilities against Assets but company improve the Debt to Equity Ratio.
- The current ratio is too low with 0.8.
- As the main functions of the company are to plan, produce, install, and test and commission the telephone exchanges and supply telephone instruments. Beside telecommunication equipment TIP is producing a variety of other products like Containers Shells, Single Phase Energy Meters, Fire Alarm equipment & Drop Wire. That's why there are no sufficient revenue generation.

Table 4.1.4.4.1: Growth

	2016	2017	2018	2019
Sales Growth	15.38%	-86.67%	0.00%	100.00%
Gross Profit/loss Growth	-7.23%	-64.07%	1.20%	-102.38%
Net Profit/loss Growth	-43.66%	-81.67%	122.73%	104.08%
Total Assets Growth	2.04%	15.57%	-2.81%	3.15%
Total Liabilities Growth	42.90%	-70.34%	274.21%	9.44%

Table 4.1.4.4.2: Ratio Analysis

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Gross Profit (loss) margin	-1915%	-1540%	-4150%	-4200%	50%
Net profit (Loss) margin	-1638%	-800%	-1100%	-2450%	-2500%
Operating expenses to Sales	3354%	2327%	21750%	19800%	13650%
Finance cost to sales	754%	520%	3650%	3650%	2150%
Debt to Equity Ratio	-1.62	-1.38	0.76	-1.38	-1.35
Current Ratio	0.67	0.05	0.21	0.15	0.82

1.15.4 **MINISTRY OF MEDIA & ENTERTAINMENT**

1.15.4.1 **PAKISTAN BROADCASTING CORPORATION**

- Provision for doubtful debts 28.45 million for three years in 2016- 2017; 36.15 million.
- Employee benefit obligations amounts to 24 million in 2017.
- Provision of slow moving and obsolete stores and spares amount to 65.3 million
- Gross Income is reducing from 5%
- Agency commission is decreasing from 2% and increased by 75% in 2019
- Cash/Bulk and other discounts revenue is reducing with very high percentage (16 million in 2016 and 5 million in 2019)
- Cost of service is very high and it is more than 1000% of revenue. From the last 2 years, this cost has been increasing
- Salaries and allowances are very high and increasing each year (Table 4.1.13.1)

Table 4.1.13.1: Cost of Service Break Up

	2017	2018	2019
Salaries & Allowances	-24%	16%	33%
Other benefits	21%	-8%	7%
Program Expenses	5%	-4%	6%
New Expenses	2%	1%	3%
Depreciation	-6%	-2%	8%

- From the last years, the expenses (selling, distribution cost & service) are increasing

- In 2019, 5 million subsidy is received from the Government but not enough to cover cost of electricity (Table 4.1.13.2)

Table 4.1.13.2: Vertical Analysis of Income Statement

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Advertisement Income	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Cost of Services	-1174%	-1168%	-898%	-1042%	-1447%
Gross Loss	-1074%	-1068%	-798%	-942%	-1347%
Selling, General & Administrative Expenses	-745%	-703%	-518%	-624%	-902%
Loss Before tax	-1819%	-1770%	-1316%	-1566%	-2249%
Subsidy from Government of Pakistan	1027%	1142%	1123%	1322%	2096%
Other Income	5%	11%	12%	11%	64%
Loss before taxation	-787%	-618%	-181%	-233%	-89%
Provision for taxation	-1%	-1%	-2%	-3%	-2%
Loss after taxation	-788%	-618%	-183%	-236%	-91%

- In liabilities, the highest amount is of pension and gratuity. It is about Rs. 24 million in 2019
- Development loan is taken by the Federal Government which worth 2,817 million..

1.15.4.2 PAKISTAN TELEVISION CORPORATION

The following is the analysis of financial statement 2018 and 2019 (due to data non-availability constraints):

- The company is in losses till 2018 but in 2019, it earned profit. The reason behind earning profit is the increase in sale revenue. This is due to the increase in license fee, included in consumer electricity bill (Asad, 2020)
- Pension payable is more than 45% of the total non-current liabilities

1.15.5 MINISTRY OF OIL & GAS

1.15.5.1 SUI SOUTHERN GAS COMPANY LIMITED (SSGC)

- The Sui Southern Gas Company Limited is losses in last 5 years, they has gross losses from 2014 to 2018 but they recovered in 2019 and in same year the equity is in negative as well, however, their net losses are consistent.
- Low growth in Sales (See Table 4.1.14.1).
- High cost of goods sold which includes: Gas development surcharge, RLNG differential margin.
- High expenses for instance administrative expenses (salaries and pensions), selling expenses, other operating expenses, increasing finance cost and taxes (sales tax and other taxes).

Table 4.1.14.1: Ratio Analysis

Rs Million	2019	2018	2017	2016	2015	2014
Trading Results						
Sales (excluding Gas Development Surcharge)	297,167	177,404	156,673	138,616	162,583	153,283
Gross (loss) / profit	2,046	-9,777	-839	-24,824	-6,436	-8,968
(Loss) / profit before tax	-16,820	-10,826	3,316	-7,840	-8,769	-5,810
(Loss) / profit after tax	-18,395	-14,848	1,336	-6,115	-5,391	-3,753
Operating Ratios						
Gross margin	0.69%	-5.51%	-0.54%	-17.91%	-4.05%	-5.85%
Pre tax margin	-5.66%	-6.10%	2.12%	-5.66%	-5.39%	-3.79%
Net margin	-6.19%	-8.37%	0.85%	-4.41%	-3.32%	-2.45%
Financial position						
Shareholders' equity	-8,022	3,406	16,082	14,146	18,827	23,867
Property, plant and equipment	129,720	120,524	114,993	96,711	73,942	70,165
Net current assets	-65,870	-43,029	-27,102	-39,333	-15,580	-5,774
Long term assets	1,649	1,870	4,601	4,470	2,241	1,955
Long term liabilities	73,522	75,959	76,409	47,702	41,776	42,479
Capital employed	38,735	59,702	71,917	42,475	44,466	48,773
Performance						
Capital expenditure	9,591	10,808	21,562	26,815	7,278	6,506

Asset turnover ratio	0.65	0.51	0.53	0.5	0.64	0.71
Fixed assets turnover ratio	2.38	1.51	1.48	1.62	2.26	2.22
Inventory Turnover	1.93	2.45	2.52	2.06	2.07	1.71
Return on equity	NA*	-152.40%	8.80%	-37.09%	-25.25%	-15.01%
Return on capital employed	-37.37%	-22.56%	2.34%	-14.07%	-11.56%	-7.27%

1.15.6 MINISTRY OF TRADING & MARKETING

1.15.6.1 UTILITY STORES CORPORATION OF PAKITAN (PRIVATE) LIMITED

- The store had been established September 03, 1971, with paid up capital of Rs 737.73 million. The aim of incorporating this entity was to procure essential goods domestic and outside resources. And to make sure the quality of product and offer lower prices.
- The store has been incurring net losses in last 4 years but it has gross profit due to subsidy. The loss in 2018 is 5,023 million and accumulated losses aggregating are 7,634 million and from 3013 USC has cumulative losses of 13.6 billion.
- The net sales (sales of commodities min sales tax) has been decreasing every year in last 4 years and the cost of goods sold is high too, it is almost equal to the revenue and sometimes exceeds the revenue stream. But due to subsidy by Government of Pakistan in order to stabilize prices of essential commodities in the market to provide relief to end consumer.
- The Cost of Goods sold includes: opening stock in trade plus purchases and direct expenses: Freight and octroi, handling charges, packing material and others and depreciation and closing stock in trade.
- The expenses are too high, the highest expense is Selling and distribution expenses and administrative expenses.
- Liabilities are increasing every years therefore, the finance cost has been increasing every year. In 2018 the equity is in negative due to accumulated losses and high liabilities.

1.15.7 FINANCE DIVISION

1.15.7.1 SME BANK

- Advances are decreasing. In 2020, capital adequacy ratio is negative 107% and it is negative from the last 5 year
- Income is not increasing with the percentage expense is increasing
- Loans and advance to customers revenue is decreasing which has the major contribution in the revenue stream
- Liabilities are increasing with 1 million each year and Equity base is less than 2 billion
- Increase in inflation and interest rate discouraged the business activities, affected the repayment capacity and behavior of borrowers
- Non-performing loans are 405 million. Non-performing loans are less than 100 billion while total advances are between 300 to 500 billion
- Investments are more than the advances and from the last 5years, investments are increasing with a very high percentage. Wholesale & trade and individuals have more than 1.5 million in non-performing advances
- Interest expense is more than the interest income (1008 million is interest expense and 739 million is interest income in 2020)

- The spread is negative that means interest rate it pays to depositors is more than it receives from consumers (See Table 4.1.16.1)

Table 4.1.16.1: Net Interest (Rs. In Million)

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Total Income	753.9	789.5	753.6	674	662.3	753.2
Interest Income	738.9	776.3	741.4	649.3	615.1	705.3

- The bank was in gross profit till 2019 (See Table 4.1.16.2). In 2020, the gross loss is due to:
 1. Income from loss and advances to employees decreased by 26%
 2. Income from investment in held to maturity securities, there is a decrease of 75%
 3. Income from deposits of financial institutions, there was a decrease of 8% and in the previous year it was increased by 204%
 4. Deposit expense is increased by 73%
 5. The average cost of deposits increased to 9.95% as compared to 6.13% in 2018
 6. 37% of total income is Managerial compensation expense

Table 4.1.16.2: Vertical Analysis of Income Statement

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Mark-up/return/interest earned	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Mark-up/return/interest expensed	61%	70%	78%	95%	147%
Net mark-up/interest (loss)/income	39%	30%	22%	5%	-47%
Provision against non-performing loans and advances-net	-10%	0%	-3%	0%	0%
Net mark-up/ interest income after provisions	49%	-1%	0%	0%	0%
NON MARK-UP/INTEREST INCOME	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Fee and commission income	2%	0%	0%	1%	1%
Dividend income	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Foreign exchange income	0%	0%	-3%		
Gain on securities	0%	32%	25%	0%	0%
Other income	0%	2%	2%	0%	0%
Total non-markup/interest income	5%	0%	0%	2%	2%
Total (loss)/income	7%	5%	2%	6%	-45%

NON MARK-UP/INTEREST EXPENSES	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Operating expenses	0%	1%	0%	116%	118%
Workers Welfare Fund	97%	8%	4%	0%	9%
Other charges	95%	40%	28%	117%	127%
Total non-markup/interest expenses	1%	0%	0%	111%	121%
Loss before provisions	0%	0%	0%	-111%	-172%
Provisions and write offs – net	97%	0%	0%	2%	-3%
LOSS BEFORE TAXATION	-41%	-42%	-30%	-112%	-169%
Taxation	1%	1%	1%	-7%	-27%
LOSS AFTER TAXATION	-42%	-43%	-48%	-105%	-142%

1.15.7.2 FIRST WOMEN BANK LIMITED

- The Bank was in losses and couldn't published any financial statement after 2017 and the company was in losses in 2017, however, we have excluded it from our analysis as the government already decided to privatize it and they are collecting bids for the band.

1.15.7.3 PAK LIBYA INVESTMENT & HOLDING COMPANY

- The company occurred loss in the FY 2018 and FY 2019 but it was in profit since 2013.
- From 2017, the interest expenses had become very high as compared to the increase in interest income. The reason may be because the interest earned on investment in available for sale of securities had declined.
- Interest earned has great fluctuations from 2012 to 2019. The highest contribution in this revenue is of investment in available for sale of securities (average 2012 to 2019 = 49% of total interest earned). The graph shows fluctuation in investment on available for sale securities is coaligned with fluctuations in total interest earned.
- The borrowing in interest expense has the highest average share in the interest expense. The reason behind increasing interest expense, is the increased interest expense of borrowings. The company's investment account in the balance sheet is also increasing with high percentage (61% increase in 2019).

- The major non markup expense is administrative expense which is almost 23% of mark up interest income. The salary, allowances and benefit increased by 8% in 2017. The executive director’s remuneration in 2017 was 11% of mark up interest earned.
- The losses are more in a year due to high provisioning (In 2013’s annual report, it has been mentioned that due to high provisioning, high losses were reported. These provision were reversed and declared as profit in 2013 due to recovery efforts made).

- Comparison of Pak Libya’s Provision against Non-performing loans & advances to other investment Companies: As the Following graph shows that the Pak Libya has the highest fluctuations in this account.

1.15.8 CABINET DIVISION

1.15.8.1 PRINTING CORPORATION OF PAKISTAN

- The sale of PCP has decreased from 395 million to 303 million during the year 2015-18 but has been increased to 663 million in 2019 (increase of 119%). The cost

of sales has been increased during the year under review. In 2019, it has been 123% of its revenue which is the increase of 14% from the last year. The further investigation is not done due to the data non-availability.

Table: Vertical Analysis of Income statement

	2016	2017	2018
Sales	100%	100%	100%
Cost of Sales	54%	106%	123%
Gross Profit	46%	-6%	-23%
G&A Expense	22%	69%	70%
Selling Expense	0%	0%	2%
Operating Profit/loss	23%	-75%	-94%
Other income	2%	1%	12%
Financial Charges	16%	49%	74%
Profit/Loss before taxation	9%	-123%	-157%
Taxation	1%	1%	1%
Profit/loss after taxation	8%	-125%	-158%
Prior year adjustments	-1%	0%	0%
Net Profit	7%	-125%	-158%
Accumulated loss	-244%	-907%	-1079%

- The trade payables are decreased from the year 2015-2019 but they are between 158% to 73% of total liabilities and equities. There are fluctuations in this account such as in a year, decreasing by 27% and in another year, decreased by 12%. The trade receivables has been decreasing from the year 2015 to 2019. There is an increase by 29% in 2016 and decrease of 35% in 2019.

Table : Vertical Analysis of Balance Sheet

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Cash & Bank Balance	51%	32%	70%	70%	70%
Trade Receivables	10%	16%	9%	9%	6%
Other Current Assets	11%	17%	17%	17%	19%
Current Assets	98%	91%	96%	96%	96%
Fixed Asset	2%	9%	4%	4%	4%
Other Non-Current Assets	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Non-Current Assets	2%	9%	4%	4%	4%

Total Assets	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Trade Payables	158%	145%	75%	75%	73%
Short Term Borrowings					
Other Current Liabilities	33%	49%	28%	28%	43%
Current Liabilities	191%	194%	103%	103%	116%
Long Term Loans	81%	101%	119%	119%	132%
Other Non-Current Liabilities	32%	48%	25%	25%	25%
Non-Current Liabilities	113%	149%	144%	144%	157%
Total Liabilities	304%	344%	247%	247%	273%
Share Capital	9%	11%	5%	5%	6%
Accumulated Profit/(Loss)	-213%	-255%	-152%	-152%	-179%
Revaluation Surplus	0%	1%	0%	0%	0%
Reserves/ Others					
Equity	-204%	-244%	-147%	-147%	-173%
Total Liabilities + Equity	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

- The long term loan has been increased by 167% and trade payables decreased from 29% to 0%. Fixed assets has only 10% increase in the same year.
- The company is unable to meet its current obligations as the current ratio is 0.82 in 2019. This ratio has increased in the years under review.
- Working capital is negative in the years under review and it has been increasing over the years.

1.15.8.2 PAKISTAN TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORPORATION

- The company sales have been decreased in the years under review. The cost of sales have increased with minimum percentage. Only in 2015, the company is in gross profit but afterwards, it is in gross loss.

- The company's current ratio is less than 1 and it has increased in 2017 and 2018 but again decreased in 2019. The working capital is in negative which means the company is not able to meet its obligations.

- Current liabilities are very high and the major proportion is of trade payables, fluctuating between 386 to 176 million. The trade receivables were decreasing during the year under review but they again started growing with minor percentage.

1.15.9 POWER GENERATION COMPANIES:

Loss Making vs. Profitable Power Generation Companies

Loss making Power Generation Companies

1.15.9.1 GENCO-III: Northern Power Generation Company Limited, Thermal Power Station, Muzaffargarh

- Northern Power Generation Company Limited owns and operates thermal power generation facilities located at Muzaffargarh, Multan and Faisalabad. Installed capacity of the generating assets is 1,921 MW.
- GENCO-III is in gross losses in last 6 years (2013 & 18) but in 2017 and 2019 the company recorded gross profit due to low cost of goods sold.
- The Net losses of GENCO-III were constant in last 7 years (2013-19) but the ratio of Net Loss Margin has been decreased in year 2019, however, the company had net profit of 0.78% in year 2017 (See Table 4.1.18.1).
- The key reason behind the net losses are the high Operating Expenses and the ratio of operating expenses to Sales has increasing trend.
- Finance cost was also high and the ratio of Finance cost to Sales has increasing trend.

- On balance sheet side, the equity position was negative due to High Liabilities against Assets but company improve the Debt to Equity Ratio.
 - The current ratio has decreasing trend.
- Policy, license for 25-30 years and get fixed return on equity and it will be expired in 2027.

Table 4.1.18.1: Ratio Analysis

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Gross Profit (loss) margin	-4.43%	4.86%	3.17%	2.07%	3.66%	0.22%	5.44%
Net profit (Loss) margin	-4.75%	4.82%	3.39%	5.78%	0.78%	2.61%	1.35%
Operating expenses to Sales	0.48%	0.58%	0.64%	1.01%	1.06%	1.05%	1.82%
finance cost to sales	4.13%	2.99%	3.23%	5.50%		0.00%	0.00%
Debt to Equity Ratio	-127.47	-13.64	1.14	0.14	1.42	1.49	1.78
Current Ratio	2.36	1.86	1.92	1.68	1.6	1.5	1.55

1.15.9.2 GENCO-I: Jamshoro Power Company Limited

- GENCO-I was incorporated in August 1998, under companies ordinance 1984 and started it's business as a Govt. of Pakistan. WAPDA owned entity from 1st March, 1999.
- This power generating company has shown bad financial performance in last few years and the in year 2019 sales decreased by 32.11%, Gross Profit Decreased by 183.06%, Net Profit decreased by 579.43%, Total assets are decreased by 18.63% and that's why liabilities are also decreased by 13.3% whereas the equity position is already in negative. On the other hand, the key expense which is Admin and general expenses is increased by 12.9% (See table 4.1.19.1).
- GENCO-I is in gross losses in 2019 the company recorded gross profit due to high cost of goods sold and in 2019 gross profit/loss margin ratio is -3.6% (See Table 4.1.19.2).

- The GENCO-I is in Net losses in 2019 net profit/loss margin ratio is -8.14%.
- The key reason behind the net losses are the high Administrative and general expenses and the ratio of Administrative and general expenses to Sales has increasing trend.
- Finance cost was also high and the ratio of Finance cost to Sales also has increasing trend.
- On balance sheet side, the equity position was negative due to High Liabilities against Assets but company improve the Debt to Equity Ratio.
- The current ratio is too low.
- On cash flow side, the Operating Cash flow to sales has increasing trend.

Table 4.1.9.2.1: Growth

	2017	2018	2019
Sales Growth	9.53%	-35.6%	-32.11%
Gross Profit/loss Growth	-165.23%	-37.3%	-183.06%
Net Profit/loss Growth	-128.49%	-58.3%	-579.43%
Administrative and general expenses growth	-4.67%	9.72%	12.93%
Total Assets Growth	16.41%	8.77%	-18.63%
Total Liabilities Growth	14.96%	9.54%	-13.30%

Table 4.1.9.2.2: Ratio Analysis

	2016	2017	2018	2019
Gross Profit (loss) margin	-5.08%	3.02%	2.94%	-3.60%
Net profit (Loss) margin	-6.85%	1.78%	1.15%	-8.14%
Administrative and general expenses to Sales	-2.50%	-2.17%	-3.70%	-6.16%
Finance cost to sales	-0.08%	-0.07%	-0.10%	-0.21%
Debt to Equity Ratio	-6.35	-6.81	-6.54	-4.88
Current Ratio	0.10	0.08	0.21	0.37
Operating Cash flow to sales	0.16%	1.70%	0.52%	3.14%

1.15.9.3 GENCO-IV: Lakhra Power Generation Company Limited

- The GENCO-IV: Lakhra Power Generation Company Limited has no revenue generation in year 2019. That's why company continues its gross loss.
- However, the company had enough other income to cover gross losses and all expenses, therefore the company is in net profit in last two years (2018 & 2019).
- This power generating company has shown bad financial performance historically, and the in year 2019 they did not record Sales, COGS and Gross Profit. However, the Net Profit increased by 3104.92%, Total assets are increased by 25% and that's why liabilities are also increased by 5.6% whereas the equity position is already in negative. (See table 4.1.9.3.1: Growth).
- The GENCO-VI has no financial ratio as its revenue figure is missing in year 2019.
- Finance cost was also high and the ratio of Finance cost to Sales also has increasing trend.
- On balance sheet side, the equity position was negative due to High Liabilities against Assets but company improve the Debt to Equity Ratio.
- The current ratio is low by 0.9 (See table 4.1.9.3.2)

Table 4.1.9.3.1: Growth

	2016	2017	2018	2019
Sales Growth	-5.34%	-12.14%	-96.11%	
Gross Profit/loss Growth	14.87%	96.69%	-94.68%	
Net Profit/loss Growth	-26.17%	161.10%	-106.73%	3104.92%
Total Assets Growth	-0.24%	-2.34%	9.64%	25.17%
Total Liabilities Growth	2.11%	8.80%	3.77%	5.65%

Table 4.1.9.3.2: Ratio Analysis

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Gross Profit (loss) margin	-25.57%	-31.03%	-69.46%	-95.00%	
Net profit (Loss) margin	-38.03%	-29.66%	-88.13%	152.50%	
Administrative and general expenses to Sales	17.56%	17.44%	21.30%	2695.00%	
finance cost to sales	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	7.50%	
Debt to Equity Ratio	-3.1	-2.96	-2.46	-2.69	-3.9

Current Ratio 0.68 0.7 0.68 0.75 0.91

**1.15.9.4 GENCO-II: Central Power Generation Company Limited,
Thermal Power Station, Guddu**

- Historically, this power generation company remained profitable. The GENCO-II generates gross profit because of high revenue stream and have gross profit due to low expenses.
- Guddu power generating company has shown best financial performance among all power generation companies, however, in last few years and the in year 2019 sales increased by 22.8%, Gross Profit increased by 10%. Net Profit also been realized (there was net loss in year 2018), Total assets are increased by 48% and that’s why liabilities are also increased by 49% whereas the equity position is already in negative (See table 4.1.9.4.1).
- GENCO-II is in gross Profit in 2019 the company recorded gross profit due to high sales and low cost of goods sold and in 2019 gross profit/loss margin ratio is 12% (See table 4.1.9.4.2).
- The GENCO-II is in Net profit in 2019 net profit/loss margin ratio is 4.5%.
- The key reasons behind the net profit are the low Operating expenses and the ratio of operating expenses to Sales is only 1.9%.
- Finance cost was also high with 5.3% of sales and the ratio of Finance cost to Sales also has decreasing trend.
- On balance sheet side, the equity position was negative due to High Liabilities against Assets but company improve the Debt to Equity Ratio.
- The current ratio is too low (0.68).

Table 4.1.9.4.1: Growth

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Sales Growth	-24.86%	13.58%	44.12%	14.01%	6.68%	22.86%
Gross Profit/loss Growth	-30.08%	-326.76%	101.85%	-3.63%	3.15%	10.20%
Net Profit/loss Growth	-113.33%	549.89%	306.12%	-68.10%	-204.75%	-191.68%
Total Assets Growth	19.82%	8.51%	9.35%	-2.53%	15.47%	58.46%

Total Liabilities Growth -3.36% 19.27% 49.38%

Table 4.1.9.4.2: Ratio Analysis

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Gross Profit (loss) margin	-6.30%	12.58%	17.63%	14.90%	14.41%	12.92%
Net profit (Loss) margin	1.35%	7.73%	21.79%	6.10%	-5.99%	4.47%
Operating Expenses to Sales	-7.65%	1.26%	1.11%	1.18%	1.20%	1.90%
finance cost to sales	0.00%	0.00%	7.80%	4.71%	13.73%	5.30%
Debt to Equity Ratio	0	0	-21.42	-25.94	-14.45	-79.25
Current Ratio	0.31	0.14	0.32	0.34	0.64	0.68

1.15.10 Industrial Estate Development

1.15.10.1 Pakistan Textile City

- The entity has been established in 2004 by public private venture with an aim to develop and operate Pakistan’s first state-of-the-art industrial zone at Port Qasim, Karachi in order to have value addition to the textile sector.
- But, this project collapsed and fail to record single rupee in revenue account in last 3 years (as the data is available from 2017-19).
- The company has no Sales and COGS therefore, no Gross Profit/loss.
- But the entity has losses due to high expenses which includes; Operating Expenses and finance cost. .

- The losses are only sum of the expenses company incurred during year without generating any revenue.
- The equity's position is also in negative in year 2019 due to huge increment in liabilities against assets.

1.16 RECOMMENDATIONS

PAKISTAN INTERNATIONAL AIRLINE

- To stop the expensive and non-profitable routes and should extend the profitable routes.
- To minimize the administrative expense, it must reduce its salaries cost and reduce the pension funds through formulating a new pension policy.
- To reduce the employees per aircraft as it is costing the company millions.
- To obtain some lease payer aircraft which will help to control the cost.
- To improve and promote the service of the company by creating new policies such as "Free Tourist Visa Policy"

PAKISTAN RAILWAY

To conclude our analysis, we have found two major reasons for losses first one is inefficient service delivery and high operating cost.

To increase revenue:

- Improve service delivery to increase sales revenue as there is pretty good demand.
- Revalue and use the wasteland which is owned by Pakistan Railways nearby Railway tracks or railway stations either commercialize it by building hotels, restaurants, shops, shopping malls etc., or sell it out to minimize cash flow gap.
- Start running Circular Rails in metropolitan areas of Pakistan (there is so much need for it).
- Start Specials trains to our neighbor countries for instance Iran, thousands of people travel to Iran every year and they need to have such transportation facility.
- Restart Good transportation via Trains there is high market potential as it's less costly and less risky for business community to transport their goods via train.

To decrease Expenditure:

- To reduce Operating Expenses (Admin and Repair and maintenance are high loss contributors from operating expenses), the Pakistan Railways can bring efficiency in service delivery for instance; improve engines, abide train schedules so that trains can arrive and departure on time and minimize wastage of resources.
- Minimize the admin expenses, as it includes salaries and pensions and Pakistan Railways has 68,727 employees and 121,000 pensioners. In 2018-19, the expenditure on pay and pension was 67.5% of the total working expenses but to reduce pensions in future they can implement new policy of giving retiree lump-sum amount at the time of retirement to save monthly pension expenses.

NATIONAL HIGHWAY AUTHORITY

- Decrease the liabilities to reduce finance cost expense
- Decrease operating expenses by changing pension policy or bring other policy for salaries
- For increasing revenue stream the NHA has to utilize the resources and commercialize the land they own by roads side for instance: build guest houses, restaurants, hotels, shops or rent the petrol pumps etc.

PAKISTAN POST OFFICE

SOEs Triage report write that the Government has included it into the Retention and restructure SOEs list.

As per the Auditor General's Report on Pakistan Post Office: Improve following accounts to improve losses, postal treasury, utility bills collection, contingencies, military and postal pension payments, bogus money orders, PLI premium receipts, shortage of cash, snatching of cash and special saving accounts etc.

- The main issue with the PPO is not cost but low growth of sales.
- Increase number of services to increase revenue.
- Bring efficiency in operations to improve service quality.
- Improve revenue recovery mechanism.
- Close loss making franchises or merge them.
- Decrease Operating Expenses and in Operating expenses they had higher admin cost decrease it and change the pension policy.
- Decrease liabilities to decrease finance cost.
- Rebrand and follow the high profitable companies' For Instance: TCS.
- Add remittance facility as they are offering financial services as well.

-
- Government office has to impose rule to post the mails via PPO only.
 - Add Riding services for instance Food Delivery.

ELECTRIC POWER DISTRIBUTION COMPANIES

- The major losses are because of low revenue stream, poor management, recovery system and infrastructure and higher operating expenses, however, we also recommend privatization for their electric supply companies but it needs to improve their losses first and we recommend following steps to improve:
- Improve bill collection.
- Collect bills from Government institutions on time as they are major users in some areas and they are paying their bills very late.
- Reduce operating expenses, by changing retirement policies for instance give lum sum at the time of retirement instead of paying every month as pensions have the major portion in admin expenses.
- Improve Transmission and Distribution network to reduce line losses.
- Improve overall infrastructure to bring efficiency in supply of an Electricity.
- Further break the companies into small electric supply companies to bring efficiency for instance K electric despite the fact that it is private company but it is working efficiently because it has only one city.

PAKISTAN STEEL MILLS

The Pakistan Steel mills company is already in the process of privatization. The analysis shows the important reasons of its potential privatization.

HEAVY MECHANICAL COMPLEX PRIVATE LIMITED

The HMC company is already in the process of privatization. The analysis shows the important reasons of its potential privatization. Also Government is calling bids to privatize Heavy Mechanical Complex (Private) Limited

STATE ENGINEERING COROPORATION (PRIVATE) LIMITED

SOEs Triage Report 2018-19 Suggested to privatize it. The company should be privatized to improve efficiency and productivity to promote the industry further.

TELEPHONE INDUSTRIES OF PAKISTAN

SOEs Triage Report 2018-19 Suggested to privatize it.

We recommend to private the TIP and then produce mobile devices and other high demand items.

PAKISTAN BROADCASTING CORPORATION

The company should do the cost cutting, invest in profitable projects and device a new policy regarding pension and retirement benefits.

SUISORTHERN GAS COMPANY LIMITED

- Increase gas prices
- Decrease UFG losses by bringing improving T &D
- UFG losses breakup and then add in recommend
- Break the company into 2-3 more gas companies to improve efficiency.
- Improve cash flows to improve overall losses.
- Improve cash collection to get rid of liabilities to decrease finance cost.

UTILITY STORES CORPORATION OF PAKISTAN (PVT) LIMITED

- The Revenues can be increased by adding more products other than food items to store, for instance consumer goods, clothing items, household products, electronic items. Other stores for example Imtiaz Super Market, Chase-up.
- Restructure the Utility store in a way to build another store as subsidiary and follow their competitor strategy and offer goods at competitive rates (competition with Imtiaz Super Market, Chase-up) to generate more cash flows.
- Decrease liabilities by generating more cash flows to finance assets. However, by decreasing liabilities the store can decrease finance cost.
- Decrease expenses by brining efficiency in store operations, change salaries and pensions policy.
- The store get subsidy named “sugar subsidy” but the amount is pending, if the store get that amount then they can somehow recover the cash flow.
- Increase cash flows by increasing number of items in store

SME BANK

- Merging with another profitable bank is also a solution to the problem of this bank but this SOEs is already in the process of privatization.

PAK LIBYA INVESTMENT COMPANY

- Improve its service to generate more revenue
- Make profitable investment such as in TFC Sukuk
- Make high transactions related to corporate finance
- Create a mutual fund

PRINTING CORPORATION OF PAKISTAN

- Move towards the product expansion

-
- Introduce some commercial product
 - Cost control to reduce the expenditures
 - Restructuring to improve operations

PAKISTAN TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORPORATION

- Efforts to increase sales through the improvement in service

POWER GENERATION COMPANIES

- There are total 4 GENCO companies (GENCO-I, II, III & IV), however, two are in losses (GENCO-I & III), and other two are generating profit (GENCO-II: Central Power Generation Company Limited, Thermal Power Station, Guddo & (GENCO-IV: Lakhra Power Generation Company Limited).
- The main issue is efficiency, the company should bring efficiency in their operations.
- Resolve plant related issues to meet targets.
- Government proposed privatization for GENCO Companies and privatization process will have 4 steps and it will be completed by June of 2023.

PAKISTAN TEXTILE CITY

- SOEs Triage Report 2018-19 Suggested to privatize it.
 - Recommendation from this report is to shut down and close company
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APPENDIX

1.17 TABLE A: LIST OF COMMERCIAL SOEs IN PAKISTAN

S.NO.	COMMERCIAL SOEs IN PAKISTAN
1	Zarai Taraqati Bank Limited
2	SME Bank
3	Industrial Development Bank Limited
4	National Bank of Pakistan
5	First Women Bank Limited
6	House Building Finance Company Limited
7	Exim Bank of Pakistan Limited
8	National Investment Trust Limited
9	Pak China Investment Company Limited
10	Pak Iran Investment Company
11	Pak Libya Holding Company (Private) Limited
12	Pak Oman Investment Company
13	Pak Kuwait Investment Company (Private) Limited
14	Pak Brunei Investment Company
15	Saudi Pak Industrial and Agricultural Investment Company Limited
16	State Life Insurance Corporation
17	National Insurance Company Limited
18	Pakistan Reinsurance Company Limited
19	Karachi Port Trust
20	Pakistan National Shipping Corporation
21	Port Qasim Authority
22	Gawadar Port Authority
23	Pakistan Railways
24	Karachi Urban Transport Corporation
25	National Highway Authority
26	Karachi Infrastructure Development Company Limited
27	Pakistan International Airlines Corporation
28	National Telecommunication Corporation

29	Pakistan Post Office
30	Pakistan Telecommunications Company Limited
31	State Engineering Corporation (Private) Limited
32	Heavy Mechanical Complex (Private) Limited
33	Karachi Shipyard and Engineering Works Limited
34	Telephone Industries of Pakistan
35	Pakistan Steel Mills Corporation (Private) Limited
36	Peoples Steel Mills Limited
37	Saindak Metals Limited
38	Pakistan Mineral Development Corporation (Private) Limited
39	Pakistan Industrial Development Corporation (Private) Limited
40	Pakistan Environmental Planning & Architectural Consultants (Private) Limited
41	National Engineering Services Pakistan (Private) Limited
42	STEDEC Technology
43	National Security Printing Company (Formerly Pakistan Security Printing Corporation (Private) Limited
44	Printing Corporation of Pakistan (Private) Limited
45	Government Holdings (Private) Limited
46	Oil and Gas Development Company Limited
47	Pakistan Petroleum Limited
48	Pak Arab Refinery Company
49	State Petroleum Refining & Petrochemical Corporation
50	Sui Southern Gas Company Limited
51	Pakistan State Oil Company Limited
52	Sui Northern Gas Pipelines Limited
53	Faisalabad Electric Supply Company Limited
54	Hyderabad Electric Supply Company Limited
55	Quetta Electric Supply Company Limited
56	Tribal Electric Supply Company Limited
57	Peshawar Electric Supply Company Limited
58	Lahore Electric Supply Company Limited
59	Islamabad Electric Supply Company Limited
60	Gujranwala Electric Power Company Limited

61	Multan Electric Power Company Limited
62	Sukkur Electric Power Company Limited
63	GENCO-I: Jamshoro Power Company Limited
64	GENCO-II: Central Power Generation Company Limited, Thermal Power Station, Guddo
65	GENCO-III: Northern Power Generation Company Limited, Thermal Power Station, Muzaffargarh
66	GENCO-IV: Lakhra Power Generation Company Limited
67	Lakhra Coal Development Company Limited
68	National Power Parks Management
69	Water and Power Development Authority
70	National Transmission and Despatch Company
71	Central Power Purchase Agency (Guarantee) Limited
72	Pakistan Electric Power Company (Private) Limited
73	Power Holding (Private) Limited
74	Export Processing Zones Authority
75	National Construction Limited
76	Pakistan Expo Centers (Pvt) Ltd
77	Pakistan Textile City
78	Trading Corporation of Pakistan (Private) Limited
79	Utility Stores Corporation (Private) Limited
80	Pakistan Agricultural Storage & Services Corporation Limited
81	National Fertilizer Corporation of Pakistan (Private) Limited
82	Pakistan Broadcasting Corporation
83	Pakistan Television Corporation Limited
84	Overseas Employment Corporation (Private) Limited
85	Pakistan Revenue Automation (Private) Limited
86	Small and Medium Enterprise Development Authority
87	Pakistan Tourism Development Corporation

1.18 TABLE B: COMMERCIAL & NON-COMMERCIAL SOES PROFIT & LOSS

TOTAL PROFIT & LOSS OF SOEs IN PAKISTAN 2015-2019 (Rs. IN MILLION)

	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19
Total SOEs Profit	276,773	206,043	258,108	275,348	337,278
Commercial SOEs Profit	274,563	202,928	254,197	271,152	333,192
Non Commercial SOEs Profit	2,210	3,115	3,911	4,196	4,086
Total SOEs Loss	-224,842	-418,083	-429,548	-513,997	-480,004
Commercial SOEs Loss	-221,776	-417,396	-416,880	-512,530	-478,515
Non Commercial SOEs Loss	-3,066	-687	-12668	-1,467	-1,489
NET PROFIT/LOSS	51,931	-212,040	-171,440	-238,649	-142,726

TOTAL PROFIT & LOSS OF SOEs IN PAKISTAN 2015-2019 (PERCENTAGE)

	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19
Commercial SOEs Profit	99.20%	98.49%	98.48%	98.48%	98.79%
Non Commercial SOEs Profit	0.80%	1.51%	1.52%	1.52%	1.21%
Commercial SOEs Loss	98.64%	99.84%	97.05%	99.71%	99.69%
Non Commercial SOEs Loss	1.36%	0.16%	2.95%	0.29%	0.31%

1.19 TABLE C: TOP-10 COMMERCIAL SOEs LOSSES IN 2015-19

Top-10 Loss Making SOEs in 2014-15

	Rs. In Million	Percentage
Quetta Electric Supply Company Limited	-35,755	15.90%
Pakistan International Airlines Corporation	-32,132	14.29%
Pakistan Railways	-27,247	12.12%
Pakistan Steel Mills Corporation (Private) Limited	-25,736	11.45%
National Highway Authority	-22,808	10.14%
Hyderabad Electric Supply Company Limited	-18,613	8.28%
Peshawar Electric Supply Company Limited	-15,981	7.11%
Lahore Electric Supply Company Limited	-13,722	6.10%
Pakistan Broadcasting Corporation	-6,390	2.84%
Pakistan Post Office	-6,331	2.82%

Top-10 Loss Making SOEs in 2015-16

	Rs. In Million	Percentage
National Highway Authority	-157,371	37.70%
Pakistan International Airlines Corporation	-45,276	10.85%
Quetta Electric Supply Company Limited	-34,608	8.29%
Hyderabad Electric Supply Company Limited	-27,246	6.53%
Pakistan Railways	-26,994	6.47%
Sukkur Electric Power Company Limited	-21,739	5.21%
Pakistan Steel Mills Corporation (Private) Limited	-18,758	4.49%
Peshawar Electric Supply Company Limited	-14,508	3.48%
Faisalabad Electric Supply Company Limited	-13,311	3.19%
Lahore Electric Supply Company Limited	-11,184	2.68%

Top-10 Loss Making SOEs in 2016-17

	Rs. In Million	Percentage
National Highway Authority	-133,488	27.46%
Pakistan International Airlines Corporation	-46,098	13.04%
Pakistan Railways	-40,702	11.05%
Lahore Electric Supply Company Limited	-37,370	8.39%
Hyderabad Electric Supply Company Limited	-27,310	7.15%
Peshawar Electric Supply Company Limited	-19,372	6.60%
Quetta Electric Supply Company Limited	-18,703	5.33%
Multan Electric Power Company Limited	-17,935	4.73%
Pakistan Steel Mills Corporation (Private) Limited	-14,852	4.23%
Faisalabad Electric Supply Company Limited	-14,219	3.13%

Top-10 Loss Making SOEs in 2017-18

	Rs. In Million	Percentage
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National Highway Authority	-140,748	27.46%
Pakistan International Airlines Corporation	-66,827	13.04%
Lahore Electric Supply Company Limited	-56,635	11.05%
Peshawar Electric Supply Company Limited	-42,986	8.39%
Faisalabad Electric Supply Company Limited	-36,622	7.15%
Pakistan Railways	-33,825	6.60%
Multan Electric Power Company Limited	-27,337	5.33%
Islamabad Electric Supply Company Limited	-24,255	4.73%
Quetta Electric Supply Company Limited	-21,701	4.23%
Hyderabad Electric Supply Company Limited	-16,041	3.13%

Top-10 Loss Making SOEs in 2018-19

	Rs. In Million	Percentage
National Highway Authority	-173,792	36.21%
Pakistan International Airlines Corporation	-56,121	11.69%
Quetta Electric Supply Company Limited	-36,832	7.67%
Pakistan Railways	-32,769	6.83%
Lahore Electric Supply Company Limited	-31,622	6.59%
Peshawar Electric Supply Company Limited	-29,263	6.10%
Multan Electric Power Company Limited	-22,782	4.75%
Zarai Taraqiati Bank Limited- Kissan Support Services (Private) Limited	-18,281	3.81%
Pakistan Steel Mills Corporation (Private) Limited	-16,550	3.45%
Sukkur Electric Power Company Limited	-10,956	2.28%

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